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Deliverable D6.2 – *The Climate Adaptation Citizen engagement digital handbook*

WP6 – Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation

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Document History

Deliverable Title	The Climate Adaptation Citizen Engagement digital handbook
Brief Description	<p>This report presents the design and development of the Climate Adaptation Citizen Engagement Digital Handbook, titled <i>Voices of Climate Adaptation</i>, produced under Task 6.2 within <i>Work Package 6 – Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation</i>. It outlines the overall workflow, structure, and implementation of the digital platform, highlighting both the editorial process and the production of video interviews filmed during the project’s co-creation workshops and then edited.</p> <p>The report also provides a detailed description of all sections of the digital handbook and the three available navigation pathways, explaining how each piece of content is closely linked to the results and tools developed within the <i>Adaptation AGORA project</i>.</p>
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Partners short names / Legal name

APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
ATC	Athens Technology Center S.A.
CIMA	Centro Internazionale di Monitoraggio Ambientale – CIMA Foundation
CMCC	Euro – Mediterranean Center on Climate Change – CMCC Foundation
ECSA	Verein Der Europaeischen Buergerwissenschaften – ECSA E.v
IBE	Fundación Ibercivis
ICLEI	ICLEI European Secretariat GMBH (ICLEI EUROPASEKRETARIAT GMBH)
IIASA	Internationales Institut fuer Angewandte Systemanalyse
SEI OX	Stockholm Environment Institute, Oxford Office Limited
SEI TAL	Sihtasutus Stockholmi Keskkonnainstituudi Tallinna Keskus
UNIGE	Université de Geneve

Abbreviation and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
ACH	Agora Community Hub
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
RAST	Regional Adaptation Support Tool
T	Task
WP	Work Package
WWF	World Wildlife Fund for Nature

1. Executive Summary

To collect, narrate, and share the stories and experiences that emerged within the *Adaptation AGORA project*, it was essential to design a communicative and engaging format, one that not only presented the project's results but also allowed audiences to connect with the citizens, stakeholders, associations, and institutions who actively contributed to the participatory process. These actors-built networks, exchanged perspectives, and acquired new knowledge to apply within their local contexts.

To meet this need, Task 6.2 of *Work Package 6 – Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation* led the creation of a Climate Adaptation Citizen Engagement digital handbook capable of narrating the project's experience and documenting the participatory processes carried out across the four pilot regions. The product was titled "[Voices of Climate Adaptation](#)" to highlight the central role of the diverse voices that shaped and enriched the project. This deliverable reports on the work conducted under Task 6.2 within WP6 of the *Adaptation AGORA Project*.

The handbook presents a multimedia, interactive collection of lessons learned, showcasing the perspectives of citizens, decision-makers, scientists, and experts. It offers a personalised pathway through the project's information, guidelines, and results, allowing users to explore content aligned with their interests while providing a dynamic and accessible narrative on citizen engagement, climate disinformation, climate science, social science, and adaptation strategies.

Developing the digital handbook required a process of knowledge integration grounded in the collaboration and cross-fertilisation among all project work packages (WP1–WP6). This interconnection enabled an iterative workflow in which Task 6.2 played a central role in collecting, harmonising, and communicating the outcomes of the project through an intuitive, user-friendly digital tool.

The website of the digital handbook can be explored through three navigation modes: by themes, geographies (the four pilot regions), by voices (a multimedia gallery that can be filtered by content type and region). The four core themes reflect the conceptual pillars of *Adaptation AGORA*. Each theme highlights key project results and the specific digital tools developed and are "Local climate adaptation and citizen engagement", "Science and Data", "Policy in the making" and "Public Awareness".

Across the four pilot regions, Italy, Germany, Spain, and Sweden, the handbook narrates participatory pathways, climate challenges, proposed solutions, and the co-creation processes facilitated by the project. Each region is framed through a distinctive narrative built around its local characteristics: landscape and geography, specific climate impacts, or the engagement strategies initiated to involve citizens and stakeholders.

The development of the digital handbook was led by the CMCC team (task leader), supported by external collaborators, a video maker, and a web designer who built the website infrastructure and

crafted a dedicated brand identity. The final product is hosted on *dataclime.com*, the CMCC platform for climate-tailored services, which also hosts one of the project's tools: the *Digital Academy on Climate Data, Risks and tools*.

At the conclusion of a project such as *Adaptation AGORA*, centred on citizen engagement, climate adaptation, and participatory approaches, the goal was to capture and convey its story through the voices of its protagonists, creating a reportage-style narrative that stands as a legacy of the project. This product bridges engagement and outreach: engagement fuels outreach, and outreach amplifies the impact of participatory activities.

2. Introduction

2.1 Project and deliverable overview

This is a deliverable of the *Adaptation AGORA Project – A Gathering place to co-design and co-create adaptation*, funded by the EU's Horizon Europe initiatives within the *Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change*. *Adaptation AGORA* aims to strengthen European climate resilience by fostering best practices in engaging citizens and stakeholders in climate adaptation and transformative processes. *Work Package 6 – Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation* ensures the effective dissemination and uptake of *Adaptation AGORA*'s outputs and results among targeted audiences, including entities external to the consortium. It raises awareness, informs the broader public about the project's activities, and builds synergies and opportunities for collaboration with other projects, initiatives, and networks.

Each task within WP6 contributes to these objectives by focusing on specific communication and dissemination actions. The overall strategy follows the Communication and Dissemination Plan developed under Task 6.1, which defines what, when, why, to whom, how, and where to disseminate, exploit and communicate project results, as well as who oversees such activities. The plan also includes Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for assessing proposed measures, along with procedures and tools for reporting activities.

Task 6.1 also includes the design and implementation of the project's visual identity, the creation of the institutional website (delivered at month (M)6), and the management of the landing page and social media accounts. Task 6.2, addressed in this deliverable, focuses on the creation of the Climate Adaptation Citizen Engagement Digital Handbook – a multimedia, interactive collection of the lessons learned throughout the project. Task 6.3 focuses on ecosystem building and clustering with other projects and initiatives. The task aims to establish synergies and foster collaboration with mapped national, European, and international projects, as well as citizen engagement initiatives, including those funded under the same Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change.

Task 6.4 addresses the exploitation, sustainability, and legacy of *Adaptation AGORA*, ensuring that the project's outcomes, tools, and knowledge continue to generate impact beyond its duration.

This deliverable will address T6.2 of the *Adaptation AGORA project*. This task aims to create the Climate Adaptation Citizen engagement digital handbook, a multimedia, interactive collection of the lessons learned by the project. The handbook serves as the outcome of a knowledge integration process that relies on the active collaboration and cross-fertilization among all WPs (WP1–WP6). This interconnection enables an iterative process, giving Task 6.2 an active role in collecting, harmonizing, and communicating the outcomes of other activities through a dynamic and user-friendly tool.

Through the project results, the Digital Handbook provides an accessible narrative that shares the experiences of actors involved in the main themes of the project: climate adaptation, tackling disinformation, and community engagement for adaptation strategies. It integrates a variety of multimedia narratives – including videos, interviews, texts and a glossary on climate adaptation. A dedicated editorial curation ensures that the content uses an effective and engaging language tailored to different audiences.

According to the Grant Agreement, the digital handbook was initially planned to be developed using the *weADAPT* technology, ensuring a customised and integrated path through project information, guidelines, and outcomes included in the *Digital AGORA*. However, during the implementation phase, this approach was strategically revised to better align with the project’s communication objectives, technical needs, and long-term accessibility strategy. Further details on this implementation and the chosen technological solution are provided in the following sections of this deliverable. The digital handbook remains available online for at least five years after the end of the project, contributing to the project’s long-term impact and legacy.

According to the Grant Agreement, the handbook was originally scheduled for delivery at the end of the project, in December 2025. However, following a positive deviation, its release was brought forward to October. This decision ensured that at least three months remained before the project’s conclusion to promote and disseminate this important output externally. The tool was published in mid-October, enabling its promotion not only through a dedicated press release, but also via participation in and presentations at a series of events. These included the *Conversazioni sul Futuro* festival held in Lecce from 16 to 18 October, the Annual Conference of the Italian Society for Climate Sciences (SISC) held in Salerno from 22 to 25 October, and the annual *Convegno Nazionale di Comunicazione della Scienza*, held at the International School for Advanced Studies (SISSA) in Trieste from 2 to 5 December. These also included workshops and online webinar organised by European projects within the network of *Adaptation AGORA project* like RESIST project (funded under the EU Mission Adaptation to Climate Change) online webinar for the Community of Practice and during TICCA4Danu workshop held in CMCC headquarter in Caserta in 27-28 November 2025. This positive deviation made it possible to reach, and already exceed by the end of the project, the KPI related to the number of website views.

2.2 Rationale behind the digital handbook

The Climate Adaptation Citizen Engagement digital handbook was conceived as a multimedia and interactive collection of the lessons learned throughout the project. Its purpose was to provide a dynamic, accessible narrative capable of sharing the experiences of the various actors involved in *Adaptation AGORA*, with a specific focus on its core themes: climate adaptation, tackling disinformation, and community engagement in adaptation strategies. To this end, the handbook integrates diverse multimedia formats like videos, interviews, a climate adaptation glossary, making the content more engaging and accessible to different audiences.

To collect and produce the multimedia narratives included in the handbook, the project adopted a deliberate strategy centred on on-site interviews with key stakeholders. Interviews were filmed not only during focus groups with specific target groups, but especially during the co-creation workshops held between January and February 2025 in all four pilot regions. Additional interviews were recorded during the final project meeting in Berlin in March 2025.

The content collection process involved close collaboration between at least a member of the project coordination team (CMCC), the Task 6.2 leader, and an external video maker. Interviews included both project team members, who provided insights on outputs and methodological approaches, and external stakeholders, whose direct experiences were essential to capturing authentic, situated narratives. A detailed overview of this workflow is provided later in the deliverable; however, it is important to note here that the editing process resulted in the production of over 70 videos, and that for each pilot region a specific narrative arc was developed, highlighting locally relevant features, challenges, and insights emerging from the collected material.

The choice to adopt a multimedia, narrative-based approach stemmed from the fundamental belief that communication is not an accessory component of *Adaptation AGORA*, but an integral part of its methodology. As argued by Gregory et al. (2008), since the 1980s the traditional view of science communication, based solely on the knowledge gap between scientists and citizens (public understanding of science), has gradually evolved towards the notion of *public engagement with science*, where scientists, citizens, and policy-makers jointly negotiate the futures of science and technology. Today, participatory models increasingly emphasise *public participation in science*, with communication serving as a process for building trust, legitimacy, and shared ownership between scientific communities and citizens (Davies & Horst, 2016; Gerber, 2014).

Adaptation AGORA embraces this perspective through an interdisciplinary and multimodal approach designed to raise awareness and engage local communities in climate adaptation processes. Communication within the project is transversal and inclusive, addressing heterogeneous audiences with diverse backgrounds. Individuals who took part in participatory activities were also invited to contribute to the narrative construction through interviews. By sharing, in their own words and experiences, the needs of their territories and the value or

limitations of their involvement, participants became co-authors of the project's collective learning process.

The combination of digital tools and locally embedded engagement activities makes *Adaptation AGORA* a shared space in which communication acts as the connective tissue linking all project pillars. One of the core principles guiding the development of the digital handbook is the conviction that communication is indispensable, particularly in the context of climate change and adaptation, because it underpins trust in science and provides the space where meaningful dialogue with citizens can take place. It is therefore foundational to the participatory processes that enable citizens and civil society to articulate their needs, concerns, and expectations regarding their territories.

As highlighted by Costantino et al. (2021), narratives, stories about how the world works, what the future may hold, and our role within it, extend cognition, generate shared knowledge across time and space, and shape beliefs, values, and actions, especially in contexts characterised by deep uncertainty. The narrative approach adopted in the handbook contributes precisely to this: transforming dispersed insights into shared, meaningful stories that support collective understanding and action on climate adaptation.

2.3 From concept to implementation: why the handbook on dataclime.com

The development of the Climate Adaptation Citizen Engagement digital handbook followed a structured workflow that combined conceptual design, technical implementation, extensive video editing and production work, and an editorial process aimed at refining and organising the contents. The handbook was conceived not only as a repository of project outputs, but also as a narrative tool capable of communicating the experiences of stakeholders and local communities.

The initial concept emerged from the project's ambition to foster citizen engagement, counter climate-related disinformation, and support locally driven adaptation strategies. During the early design phase, the project team defined the target audiences, the core thematic areas, and the types of content to be included. The final structure includes video interviews, longform written texts, authorial images, and photographs from workshops and the four pilot regions, together with a glossary developed within WP6 to support a shared understanding of key terminology.

The decision to rely on these specific multimedia formats was informed by evidence showing that accessible, narrative-driven, and visually rich communication enhances engagement and supports different learning preferences. Multimedia storytelling, by combining textual, visual, and experiential elements, helps make climate adaptation more tangible and relatable for a wide range of audiences. Research highlights that communication grounded in narrative techniques, such as analogies, personal stories, and concrete examples, can be particularly effective in influencing beliefs, perceptions, and behavioural intentions (Marx et al., 2007). In this sense, the handbook does not merely inform, it connects, contextualises, and facilitates deeper engagement with the project's themes. As Morris et al. (2019) argue, effectively communicating climate change to diverse, non-

scientific audiences requires alternative approaches that extend beyond traditional informational messaging.

This is especially pertinent given that climate change often elicits low engagement, even among concerned groups. While factual information (e.g., scientific consensus) can be persuasive for some, research also shows that it may increase resistance in others. Morris et al. (2019) demonstrate that climate narratives structured as stories, rather than as informational texts, promote pro-environmental behaviour by facilitating experiential processing and strengthening affective engagement, which can act as a trigger for action. Similarly, Golderg et al. (2019) show that “experiencing” scientific consensus through short videos represents a promising strategy for improving public understanding of climate change and support for related policies. Their findings reinforce the idea that videos can serve as a powerful medium for conveying scientific agreement: vivid and high-quality messages tend to elicit stronger cognitive elaboration and are more easily integrated into existing memory structures (Guadagno et al., 2011; Petty & Cacioppo, 1986). Video quality can also enhance perceptions of credibility and trustworthiness, two factors known to significantly influence the persuasiveness of a message (Harris et al., 2018; Petty & Cacioppo, 1986).

While the original plan (as stated in the Grant Agreement) was to develop the handbook using the *weADAPT* platform, the implementation strategy was revised to better meet technical requirements, communication objectives, and long-term accessibility goals. *WeADAPT* microsites are websites with their own branding, customised design, and a predefined set of features such as interactive maps displaying case studies, users, and organisations, as well as content types including articles, courses, case studies, events, and blogs. The platform also strongly supports user interaction through forums, comments, and follow options.

However, these characteristics left limited room for integrating a large volume of multimedia materials and offered little flexibility for building a highly customised web environment. Our ambition was to create a handbook with a strong and recognisable identity, one that would be clearly connected to the *Adaptation AGORA* project while also capable of having a life of its own beyond the project’s duration. For these reasons, the decision was made to host the handbook on *dataclime.com*. Later in this deliverable, we describe what *dataclime.com* is and why hosting the handbook on this domain was considered strategically relevant for the project’s long-term legacy.

As mentioned earlier, the implementation and framing of the digital tool also relied on a dedicated editorial approach, ensuring that the content remained accessible, clear, and engaging for diverse audiences. A visual identity aligned with the *Adaptation AGORA* brand was applied across all components to guarantee coherence with the broader project communication framework.

Draft versions of the handbook were tested with project partners to assess usability and clarity. Feedback was incorporated iteratively, refining the layout, navigation structure, and presentation of multimedia content. The resulting digital handbook offers a comprehensive, interactive, and visually engaging resource. It serves as a practical tool for sharing the project’s lessons learned,

guiding citizen engagement processes, and supporting *Adaptation AGORA*'s broader objective of fostering climate resilience through participatory and community-centred approaches.

2.4 Link with Adaptation AGORA objectives and other WPs

A key aim of *Adaptation AGORA* was to strengthen regions and communities engaged in climate adaptation by leveraging participatory and deliberative processes, providing access to key resources and tools for capacity building, and enabling peer-to-peer networking, discussion, knowledge sharing, learning, and co-production. These processes were facilitated through the co-development of a *Digital AGORA* (WP3) – an open online space for democracy and knowledge co-production, with areas for discussion, exchange, and sharing of questions and updates. Outputs from these processes fed into specific guidelines and the comprehensive digital handbook.

The project served as a hub for co-designing and co-creating innovative climate adaptation solutions with local communities and stakeholders. Target communities not only hosted but actively contributed to project activities, identifying vulnerabilities and gaps in adaptive capacity through climate vulnerability assessments (WP2) and participating in co-design and co-creation of solutions. Transdisciplinary frameworks and cross-sectoral approaches were used to map stakeholder perspectives, identify needs and conflicts, and reach compromises on adaptation measures such as municipal climate adaptation plans, early warning systems, or nature-based solutions for flood risk reduction (WP2 and WP3).

This network of citizens, stakeholders, and regions was encouraged to engage with the Mission as frontrunners, accelerating their transition towards climate resilience and building capacities to understand, prepare for, and manage climate-induced risks (WP2), supported by capacity-building initiatives (WP5). Participants discussed engagement alternatives and adaptation solutions through workshops, public meetings, and roundtables with multiple stakeholders. The outputs of this co-production process were communicated at local, regional, and pan-European levels and integrated into the Climate Adaptation Citizen Engagement digital handbook (WP6).

The handbook provides a multimedia, interactive collection of lessons learned, sharing the experiences of citizens, decision-makers, scientists, and experts. It offers a personalized path through the project's information, guidelines, and results, enabling users to explore content relevant to their interests while providing a dynamic and user-friendly narrative on citizen engagement, disinformation, climate science, social science, and adaptation strategies.

The Climate Adaptation Citizen Engagement digital handbook is the result of a knowledge integration process built on the active collaboration and cross-fertilisation among all work packages (WP1–WP6). This interconnection enables an iterative workflow in which Task 6.2 plays a central role in collecting, harmonising, and communicating the outcomes of other project activities through a dynamic and user-friendly tool.

The handbook drew extensively on activities carried out in the four pilot regions within *WP2 – Co-Design and Co-Creation of Innovative/Improved Tools/Actions for Local Communities Engagement*. Within Task 2.3 (Co-evaluate innovative mechanisms and approaches for citizen engagement in climate change adaptation), at least three face-to-face focus groups with citizens and civil society organisations and one co-creation workshop per pilot region were organised, involving citizens, civil society, academics, experts, and policymakers. These activities evaluated the innovative engagement mechanisms identified in *WP1 - Mapping citizens engagement practices to improve Climate Resilience* and integrated into the *Digital AGORA* (Task 3.3). The evaluation framework developed in Task 3.2 (D3.2) was applied to assess the effectiveness of citizen and stakeholder engagement methodologies. The results of these co-evaluation activities fed back into *WP3* to further enrich the *Digital AGORA* and subsequently informed the development of the handbook.

Additional contributions came from Task 2.4 (Co-design and co-create innovative soft climate adaptation solutions), which focused on co-designing and co-creating soft climate adaptation solutions together with citizens and stakeholders in the four pilot regions. Adaptation strategies suitable to local needs, identified in Task 1.3 (Compile and analyse capacity-building resources for climate change adaptation and fighting disinformation campaigns) and the outcomes of Task 2.1 (Build local communities through the empowerment of citizens and stakeholders in assessing local climate vulnerability) formed the basis for these co-design and co-creation activities. These activities included at least three co-design focus groups and one co-creation workshop per region. The beta version of the gamified mobile app (Task 2.2 – Empower and involve citizens to tackle disinformation) supported participants' learning on climate-adaptation topics. The outcomes of Task 2.4 directly informed *WP6* and fed into the handbook.

Resources collected within Task 5.1 (Co-produce capacity-building resources) represented an additional core component of the content integrated into Task 6.2. The handbook also included direct links to the outputs of Task 5.4 (Connect the dots: translate insights and lessons learned on capacity building), which produced a series of one-pagers compiling all capacity-building materials developed under *WP5* and made publicly available through the [Zenodo platform](#). Lastly, a glossary on climate adaptation developed within *WP6* was incorporated into the final version of the handbook to ensure that access to specialised terminology and scientific concepts remained smooth, guided, and accessible for a broad audience.

Moreover, the handbook is fully aligned with the fundamental principles guiding the *Adaptation AGORA* project, including Horizon Europe's open science guidelines. Principles of openness and transparency underpin all research activities, encouraging sharing and collaboration from the earliest stages and throughout the project. Open and transparent practices are enforced in compliance with Horizon Europe's open science policy, fostering the use of the Open Research Europe (ORE) platform and open repositories for research outputs. All project results, including the digital handbook, are made available within the *AGORA* digital environment whenever possible.

3. Concept and Design of the Digital Handbook

3.1 Workflow and collaboration structure

The development of the digital handbook required close collaboration among professionals with diverse and complementary expertise. A crucial early step was the selection, through a dedicated open call, of a video maker who would support the project team throughout the entire implementation period. This decision was strategic not only for ensuring systematic photo and video documentation but also for guaranteeing a coherent and recognisable visual identity across all multimedia components of the handbook. Having a single professional responsible for capturing and producing audiovisual materials ensured a consistent authorial style, preventing fragmentation of visual language and maintaining uniformity throughout the final product.

The videomaker worked alongside the *Adaptation AGORA* team members from CMCC (Task 6.2 leaders) during all co-creation workshops in the four pilot regions. Interviews with stakeholders were filmed during the following events:

- **Rome**, co-creation workshop – 17 January 2025
- **Malmö**, co-creation workshop – 25 January 2025
- **Dresden**, co-creation workshop – 4 February 2025
- **Zaragoza**, co-creation workshop – 11 February 2025

An additional round of interviews was conducted during the final internal project meeting held in **Berlin** on 6–7 March 2025.

In parallel, a second open call was launched to recruit a web developer and web designer responsible for the technical development and graphic design of the digital handbook.

A key component of the workflow for developing the digital handbook was the close and continuous collaboration established with the web developer and designer. The process began with an in-depth introductory meeting aimed at presenting the *Adaptation AGORA* project in detail, its themes, objectives, methodological approach, and digital tools. During this phase, we also shared the full set of project brand identity materials, which served as an initial reference point for shaping the visual direction of the handbook.

From the outset, we discussed the types of content and structural elements we envisioned for the platform, drawing inspiration from [Climate Literacy](#), another CMCC website whose architecture closely reflected the dynamic, modular experience we intended to achieve. A subsequent phase focused on the technical implementation: hosting and domain selection, as well as the identification of a suitable video-hosting solution that would allow embedding multimedia content without overloading the website.

Once the initial concept, references, and materials were reviewed by the developer, we received a preliminary work plan. The development process spanned approximately eight months, from March

to early October, and followed an iterative structure. Using Figma, the web designer shared an initial structural draft that already captured the key elements we aimed to implement:

- the three navigation pathways (Themes, Geographies / Pilot Regions, and People),
- the content types (long-form thematic texts, region-specific descriptions of participatory processes and adaptation solutions, multimedia materials), and
- the glossary developed by SEI under WP6.

To further refine the sitemap, we provided a preliminary version of the main menu and the set of overarching themes to be developed:

1. *Local climate adaptation and citizen engagement*
2. *Science and data*
3. *Public awareness*
4. *Policy-making*

Based on this input, the designer delivered the first complete sitemap and an interactive wireframe visualising the initial menu structure. From the beginning, our aim was to create a fluid, dynamic, and highly navigable digital environment, markedly different from the more institutional project websites. This vision also guided the decision to develop a separate brand identity and a custom name for the handbook, enabling it to remain connected to *Adaptation AGORA* while standing as an autonomous product. The naming and branding process is described in detail in a dedicated section later in this deliverable.

The following stage consisted of an iterative design process involving multiple proposal rounds from the designer and structured feedback from the internal project team. Three distinct user interface design directions were presented (Appendix A), each supported by visual references, example websites (for structure, navigation, and interaction), sketches, and sample layouts for the homepage and theme page. All proposals used free Google Fonts.

Option 1 – Editorial

Inspired by archives and printed materials (notebooks, binders, index cards), this concept framed the handbook as a structured notebook collecting the various phases of the *Adaptation AGORA project*. The key visual feature was the header's circular and linear elements, recalling binder holes. This was the proposal furthest from the *Adaptation AGORA* identity.

Option 2 – Dynamic

This proposal used the *Adaptation AGORA* colour palette, both in solid tones and gradients, evoking movement and transition, an effect suited to interactive elements and animations. The typography combined Poppins for headings and Instrument Sans for body text, chosen for improved readability over Roboto.

Option 3 – Immersive

In this direction, circular shapes from the *Adaptation AGORA* logo were extended into rounded-corner image treatments and UI components (buttons, boxes, etc.). The logo appeared in the header, broken into connected semicircles that could evolve into a visual grammar (patterns, icons) for identifying themes and content groups. Fonts used in this option were Poppins and Roboto Flex.

Following internal discussion, Option 2 was selected. At this point, it became evident that the handbook would benefit from a distinct visual identity, leading to the development of a dedicated logo, one able to reference the *Adaptation AGORA* project while allowing the handbook to diverge from institutional fonts and graphic elements.

Within Option 2, a key design choice, approved as a deliberate departure from the project's original branding, was the use of the pilot-region colours not at full saturation, but reinterpreted through colour gradients. This decision introduced a more dynamic visual identity while maintaining a clear connection to the *Adaptation AGORA* palette.

The implementation phase progressed with the development and sharing of desktop prototypes, followed by mobile versions of the interface. In parallel, the integration of textual content, videos, and images into the web pages began, allowing the team to assess layout, usability, and the overall visual coherence of the evolving platform.

At the same time, a substantial effort was dedicated to the editing of the video interviews, carried out jointly with the videomaker. This process unfolded alongside the design and refinement of the new branding. Each video includes an opening frame aligned with the visual style of the site's homepage in the case of thematic videos. For videos related to the pilot regions, the colour gradients applied to graphical elements and opening screens correspond to the specific palette of each pilot area, ensuring that every contribution is clearly and consistently localised, also visually, within its geographical context.

A detailed description of the interviews and the full workflow adopted for video editing is provided in the *Voices* chapter of this deliverable.

3.2 Technical framework and integration

3.2.1 Hosting on Dataclime and link with Digital AGORA

As previously mentioned, the decision was made not to develop the handbook using the *weADAPT* technology. Instead, the digital handbook is hosted on *Dataclime.com*, a platform developed and maintained by the CMCC. *Dataclime* is an operational environment designed to transform climate data into accessible, tailored information for users with diverse skills and needs. By managing the entire climate-information production chain internally, the platform delivers a wide range of Climate Services.

Dataclime also hosts another digital tool developed within the *Adaptation AGORA* project: the *Digital Academy on climate data, risks and tools*. Hosting the digital handbook within this ecosystem offered greater flexibility in development and ensured the long-term sustainability of the product. In fact, it allows the handbook to remain fully operational for up to five years after the end of the project, supported directly by the internal team who contributed to its creation. Additionally, the digital handbook serves as a central hub for the project's outputs, providing direct access to all other digital tools developed within *Adaptation AGORA*, including the two digital academies and the mobile app on climate misinformation, and offering a direct link to the *Digital AGORA*, which connects to the AGORA Community Hub developed by SEI using the *weADAPT* infrastructure.

Several technical aspects were also considered to ensure legal compliance with data-protection regulations, particularly the GDPR. The platform uses CookieYes, a consent-management tool that allows websites to comply with cookie laws by displaying cookie banners, managing user consent preferences, and automatically blocking non-essential cookies until consent is given. Users can easily access and modify their cookie settings, ensuring transparency and control over personal data.

A dedicated privacy-information page provides all details regarding personal data processing pursuant to Article 13 of the GDPR. The CMCC Foundation acts as the Data Controller, and all processing activities are carried out by its internal staff in the role of content managers. For website analytics, the handbook relies on Matomo, an open-source analytics platform that respects user privacy by anonymizing personal data and not sharing it with third parties. Matomo tracks visits, pageviews, and user interactions, providing insights into site performance while remaining fully GDPR-compliant.

3.2.2 Use of YouTube channel

At the end of the multimedia content collection and editing process, the project had produced a substantial number of videos, approximately 70 in total. To ensure seamless and efficient access to these materials within the handbook, the team decided to host the videos on the project's YouTube channel and embed them directly into the website. Using an external platform like YouTube was essential because hosting all videos directly on the site would have significantly slowed down page loading times. This approach not only guaranteed proper playback and faster navigation but also increased visibility for one of the project's social media channels, driving additional traffic to the YouTube channel and enhancing overall audience engagement.

3.3 Visual identity, branding and naming

During the development process it became evident that the digital handbook required a distinct visual and conceptual frame, one that remained connected to the *Adaptation AGORA project* identity yet stood apart as a recognisable and independent product. The aim was to give the handbook a strong and coherent identity that reflected the identity the editorial and content-creation team was actively shaping throughout its development: not merely a passive collection of

best practices and lessons learned, but a digital, multimedia narrative of lived experiences, voiced directly by the people who contributed to and shaped the project.

To capture this idea, the team proposed giving the tool its own name. Several naming options were developed and presented to project partners during the General Assembly held in March 2025 in Berlin. During the presentation, which showcased the evolving set of multimedia materials produced throughout the co-creation workshops, a live poll was conducted using Mentimeter. The results (see Fig. 1 and Fig. 2) showed a clear preference for *Climate Adaptation Voices*. Following further internal discussion, this was refined into *Voices of Climate Adaptation*, a formulation that places stronger emphasis on the centrality of people’s experiences and voices, rather than solely on the thematic domain of climate adaptation itself.

Figure 1 Results of the Mentimeter live poll

Responses

Figure 2 Results of the Mentimeter live poll

Once the name was agreed upon, the next step in the design and interface development process was to create a dedicated logo derived from the original *Adaptation AGORA* identity. The web designer provided several proposals (Appendix B), based on two main directions:

1. **A symbol + logotype**, featuring four arches representing the four pilot regions or an abstracted form inspired by the *Adaptation AGORA* trademark.
2. **A logotype-only option**, using distinctive bold typefaces to emphasise the title.

Each proposal explored different typographic combinations, including Poppins (already used in the *Adaptation AGORA* identity), Uncut Sans (also free and proposed as an alternative), and PolySans Bulky, a bold and characterful font suited for titles. A final option which incorporated the *Adaptation AGORA* trademark by using it as an asterisk-like symbol, was also tested; however, it proved less effective at small sizes and did not fully convey the intended meaning.

The version that ultimately convinced the team is the one shown in Fig. 3 and visible on the homepage. This option retains the use of Poppins for consistency with the *Adaptation AGORA* brand, while introducing a symbol composed of four arches. The design echoes the geometric forms of the original project trademark but arranges them in a way that visually resembles quotation marks, an intentional choice, evoking the concept of “voices” and direct testimonies. At the same time, the four arches symbolically represent the four pilot regions where the core project activities took place. Appendix B presents four logo options, each paired with a different user interface proposal. The final choice was the Option A with Logo 1, featuring the *Poppins* font and the four arches.

Voices of Climate Adaptation

Figure 3 Voices of Climate Adaptation Logo

4. Structure of the Website and Visual Languages

4.1 Three levels of navigation

Voices of Climate Adaptation was designed with three distinct navigation paths, allowing users to explore its content through themes, geographies, and people.

1. Thematic Navigation

The platform is structured around four core themes, which reflect the main areas addressed throughout the *Adaptation AGORA* project (Fig. 4). These pillars guided the development of the project's work packages and related tasks:

- Local Climate Adaptation and Citizen Engagement
- Science and Data
- Public Awareness
- Policy in the Making

These themes offer a lens into the adaptation journey undertaken by local communities and citizens as they confront the impacts of climate change. Adaptation emerges not only as a necessary response but as an opportunity for collective growth, where science, policy, awareness, and active citizenship come together to shape resilient and empowered communities.

Themes

These themes offer a lens into the journey of adaptation that local communities and citizens are undertaking together to face the impacts of climate change. More than just a response, adaptation becomes an opportunity for collective growth, where science, policy, awareness, and active citizenship come together to shape resilient, empowered communities.

Figure 4 Thematic navigation on the website

2. Geographic Navigation

The second way to explore the platform is through geographies (Fig. 5), referring to the four pilot regions and their respective cities where most focus groups and co-creation workshops took place. These regions are:

- Italy – Rome
- Spain – Zaragoza
- Germany – Dresden
- Sweden – Malmö

From these four corners of Europe come powerful stories of climate adaptation, told directly by those experiencing it. These insights represent the outcomes of *Adaptation AGORA*'s work across diverse contexts, engaging local communities and a broader network of more than 35 follower cities and institutions. Together, they confront place-based climate challenges and co-create practical, inclusive solutions designed to foster collaboration, exchange best practices, and strengthen public awareness.

Pilot regions

From the four corners of Europe: Italy, Germany, Sweden, and Spain, come powerful stories of climate adaptation, told through the voices of those living it.

These inspiring experiences are the result of Adaptation AGORA's work across diverse regions, engaging local communities and a broader network of over 35 followers. Together, they're tackling place-based climate challenges and co-creating practical, inclusive solutions, designed to foster collaboration, share best practices, and raise awareness.

[Explore](#)

Figure 5 Navigation by pilot regions on the website

3. People-Based Navigation (Voices)

The third navigation mode focuses on people, the protagonists who actively contributed to the project (Fig. 6). This includes members of the *Adaptation AGORA* team, but especially external stakeholders across the four pilot regions who shared their ideas, emotions, feedback, and even their faces to bring this platform to life through interviews. This section was later renamed “Voices” to highlight the central role of personal testimonies. Users can explore a gallery of multimedia content, video interviews and photographs, that prioritises firsthand narratives over text-based descriptions. This section lets users meet the people behind the process: project partners, local stakeholders, policymakers, institutions, NGOs, academics, and everyday citizens. Each voice offers a unique perspective, contributing to the shaping of place-based adaptation pathways. Together, they bring to life the rich collective effort driving local resilience across Europe.

Voices

Meet the people behind the process, from project team members to local stakeholders, policymakers, institutions, NGOs, academics, and everyday citizens. Each voice offers a unique perspective, sharing their experiences, ideas, and contributions to shaping place-based adaptation journeys. Together, they bring to life the rich, collective effort driving local resilience across Europe.

[Explore](#)

Figure 6 Navigation by People on the website

These three navigation modes also represent the main menu categories of the platform (Fig. 7), alongside the Glossary and About sections, which will be discussed in greater detail later in this deliverable.

Figure 7 Main Menu of the platform

4.2 Visual languages

The visual languages used throughout the platform follow a deliberate and structured logic. At least two distinct visual registers are employed, each carrying a specific meaning and serving a particular purpose depending on the section of the site in which it appears.

On the homepage, the visual language relies on Creative Commons, free-use satellite imagery, always accompanied by appropriate credits (Fig. 8). The use of satellite images is intentional: the homepage provides a broad, high-level view of the main themes that will later be explored in depth within their dedicated pages. Visually, this creates a transition from a wide, general perspective to a more focused and specific one.

Figure 8 Example of a satellite image used on the website’s homepage. Photo by USGS

As users move into the theme pages and pilot region pages, the visual register shifts from general to specific. These sections feature original, authorial photographs taken by the video maker during the co-creation workshops, as well as contextual images of the cities hosting the project activities.

This creates a gradual progression in visual detail:

- **Pilot region pages** use contextual city photographs to situate the narrative geographically (Fig. 9).
- **Theme pages** reach the highest level of specificity, showcasing images captured during the workshops themselves, highlighting the people, processes, and environments that shaped the project (Fig. 10).

Through this layered approach, the visual identity accompanies the user from a broad, macro-level view of climate adaptation down to the concrete, lived experiences at the core of the project.

Figure 9 Example of picture used on one of the pilot regions pages; Photo by Pierluigi Giorgi

Figure 10 An example of a picture used on one of the thematic pages; Photo by Pierluigi Giorgi

4.3 Languages and Translations

Inclusivity has been one of the fundamental pillars guiding all activities carried out within the *Adaptation AGORA project*. This principle has shaped not only the involvement of diverse societal groups, such as individuals with a migration background, people with disabilities, or those living with chronic illnesses, but also a consistent effort to make project outputs accessible to as many people as possible.

For Voices of Climate Adaptation, this commitment translated into offering the possibility to navigate the platform not only in English, but also in the main languages spoken across the consortium: Italian, Spanish, German, and Swedish, the translation is available through a dedicated automated widget integrated on the website (Google Language Translator).

Languages can be set from the lower part of the menu. Moreover, several interviews were conducted in their original language, both to preserve authenticity and to reflect the linguistic identity of the cities and regions where project activities took place. To ensure that these contents are accessible to the broadest possible audience, all interviews were translated and subtitled in English.

This multilingual work represented a crucial component of the editing workflow. It required the active involvement of the internal project team, as well as the contribution of consortium partners who assisted with translations and with identifying which interview segments to keep, remove, or connect to ensure that each video conveyed a coherent and meaningful narrative. Through this collaborative and inclusive approach, Voices of Climate Adaptation reflects not only the diversity of the communities engaged in the project but also the project's commitment to making their stories understandable and accessible across linguistic boundaries.

5. The four themes

5.1 Introduction and link with project results

Climate change is an interdisciplinary phenomenon, impacting various sectors and communities within a single moment. To address climate change, adaptation solutions must also be interdisciplinary, thus, a core aspect of the *Adaptation AGORA project* involves applying various methods to engage a range of communities and co-produce adaptation solutions. The themes section of the Digital Handbook showcases this aspect of *Adaptation AGORA*, highlighting project insights related to four key themes: Citizen Engagement and Climate Adaptation, Science and Data, Public Awareness, and Policy in the Making. This section was established to share stories from the project Pilot regions and offer key insights into how these four themes are often intertwined and how they each enhance local communities.

The four themes within this section also relate to the main work packages of the project. WPs 1, 2, 3, and 5 combine the aspect of citizen engagement and climate adaptation. Efforts from these WPs resulted in the mapping of citizen engagement and climate adaptation methods and resources, which fuelled all of the project events. Work from these WPs also culminated in the organisation and implementation of Pilot region events. These events within the Pilot regions produced insights found in the Science and Data theme, and work carried out by WP4 focused on climate policy, fuelling the Policy in the Making theme. The intertwining aspect of the Themes section within the Digital Handbook reflects the interconnectedness of the project WPs and activities. Many of the WP events and initiatives built from the work done by other project WPs. Each of the themes relates to

a core aspect of the *Adaptation AGORA project*, with each one being found throughout project WPs, activities, results, and tools.

Throughout the themes sections, project results and insights are provided. Background information on climate, policy, and engagement is given to provide a framework for the significance of *Adaptation AGORA's* activities and results. As many project results have been published across scientific disciplines, a narrative approach was taken within the themes section to share the project results in a digestible and approachable way to increase the likelihood of engagement among the general public and promote the accessibility of project information across various sectors. Photos from project events and video interviews from project members are included to provide visuals and to deliver more context and insight, and links to the glossary on various terms are also included to foster further learning among users.

5.2 Local Climate adaptation and citizen engagement

The first theme titled, Local Climate Adaptation and Citizen Engagement, relates to connecting citizen engagement and climate change adaptation. As a major aspect of the *Adaptation AGORA project*, this theme was critical in reflecting the work carried out over the course of the project. Throughout this theme, project results from the different Pilot regions are showcased, and videos highlighting interviews from project members are linked throughout to provide further insights. The theme begins with an overview of adaptation and its importance within climate change. As climate impacts continue to worsen, adaptation continues to be a significant factor in fostering climate resilience. As climate change impacts can vary depending on geographical, political, and socioeconomic factors, climate solutions must, therefore, be tailored towards the needs of local communities. Climate change adaptation provides flexible solutions and can be used to achieve this tailor-made approach that addresses the needs and vulnerabilities of different communities. Hard and soft adaptation methods are then introduced, to present the variety of climate adaptation.

Local Climate Adaptation and Citizen Engagement

Charles Darwin considered adaptability the most important skill. “It is not the strongest of the species that survives, nor the most intelligent that survives. It is the one that is most adaptable to change,” he said.

Figure 11 A screenshot of the opening theme section on Local Climate Adaptation and Citizen Engagement

The message is then drawn back to the need for climate adaptation within local communities. Citizen engagement is essential in implementing effective and widespread climate adaptation, and this correlation is intentionally highlighted throughout this theme, mentioning that citizen engagement can call attention to climate hazards and vulnerabilities that are often not addressed in climate adaptation. Attention is given to the lack of citizen engagement within adaptation initiatives, and the need for diverse and tailor-made engagement methodology. Deliverable 1.2 and a video on the best practices in citizen engagement for climate action are linked here, to showcase *Adaptation AGORA*’s recommendations for citizen engagement and project activities related to citizen engagement. Capacity building is also highlighted. Another significant aspect to *Adaptation AGORA* and a major theme of many project activities, capacity building is an important feature of adaptation. A video from the WP5 leader is linked in this section, which provides more background to capacity building within *Adaptation AGORA*.

Barriers to effective citizen engagement and climate adaptation, like climate disinformation, are also explained in this theme. Disinformation has become a significant issue within climate change communication over the past decade. Understanding the complexity of climate adaptation is needed to create effective adaptation initiatives. A look into the social aspect of climate adaptation

is provided in this theme, as creating interdisciplinary solutions is essential to having robust and equitable climate action. The Pilot region Malmö is highlighted here with a video interview of one of the project members. This video highlights the need for a holistic approach to climate adaptation and showcases how *Adaptation AGORA* incorporates social science within project activities.

A look into the EU Mission's support of local adaptation is described next. Given that the *Adaptation AGORA project* is a Horizon Europe project and is part of the EU Mission on climate adaptation, this was essential to mention within the Digital Handbook. This next section goes over how the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change supports EU regions, cities, and local authorities in building climate resilience through understanding climate risks, developing pathways for preparation, and implementing innovative solutions. *Adaptation AGORA's* affiliation with the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change is established and the Regional Adaptation Support Tool (RAST) is explained. The RAST model was integral to many of the project's events. Deliverable 5.1 that details the RAST Model application within project events is linked in this section, along with a video from the project manager that gives a deeper explanation of the EU Mission for adaptation and *Adaptation AGORA's* role in supporting the Mission. Continuing off the narrative of EU climate action, the theme then dives into European's perspective on climate change. The issue remains among some of the top concerns of Europeans, and there is much support across the EU to tackle the climate crisis. Having widespread support of climate action reinforces the importance of involving local communities in climate adaptation.

This theme ends with showcasing project resources that help foster citizen engagement in climate adaptation. Participating in climate action can be intimidating, and while there is much information available, it can quickly become overwhelming and can even discourage participation. This is where many of the digital tools and resources provided by the *Adaptation AGORA* are highlighted. Video interviews on the Digital Academies are linked here to show their importance in supporting climate education and fostering climate engagement. This last section of the Local Climate Adaptation and Citizen Engagement theme is framed as the circle of the climate movement, summarizing the points made throughout the theme, and showcasing the steps of climate action: building awareness, sharing that awareness with others, and ending with sparking further participation among the community. The theme ends with a video interview highlighting adaptation as an opportunity.

The Local Climate Adaptation and Citizen Engagement theme encapsulates the core aims of the *Adaptation AGORA project* and begins the Digital Handbook with a detailed overview of the project results and tools.

5.3 Science and Data

The Science and Data theme showcases the importance of understanding climate data when developing adaptation initiatives. As one of *Adaptation AGORA's* Digital Academies focuses on how to understand climate science and data, this theme was important to incorporate within the Digital Handbook.

The theme begins by linking science and policy, establishing that science and data must be incorporated throughout climate policy to create effective action. However, science and policy are often thought of separately and are rarely incorporated together. This leads to a video interview that establishes the need for climate data as a backbone to climate policy and action. This point is expanded upon, as the theme articulates that data-driven policy helps governments utilize resources efficiently, effectively measures impact and reduces costs. Another video interview is linked here and explains how to turn data into successful decision-making.

After it is established that climate data is necessary for effective climate action, the theme acknowledges that scientific data is not always accessible or easily understood by policymakers. Therefore, the need for continuous dialogue between scientists and policymakers is essential in building climate policy. The project’s role in bridging this gap is highlighted, and a video on the *Digital Academy on Climate Data, Risks and Tools* is linked to showcase how this academy helps bridge this gap by providing education on how to understand and use climate data. This Digital Academy is further explained below the video, with a detailed overview of the Academy and the various resources it provides, like the citizen science section and the climate modules.

One of the main ways Adaptation AGORA directly addresses the gap between science and policy is through the Digital Academies. In the [Academy on Climate Data Risks & Tools](#), interested users can find accurate and easy to understand climate information on a range of topics, like adaptation, [citizen science](#), and climate justice. The Academies go a step beyond simply providing information. These

Figure 12 Screenshot of the section related to the Digital Academy within Science and Data theme

The theme then dives into Pilot region insights, showcasing the various workshops, webinars, and group sessions that were held over the course of the project. Various videos and pictures from Pilot events are included throughout this section. Resources and outputs stemming from these Pilot activities are linked here, like the Adaptation Strategy that was developed in collaboration with the Roman municipality and the vulnerability report that was created during a workshop in Zaragoza, Spain. A video describing how *Adaptation AGORA* fosters knowledge sharing via its digital tools, like the Agora Community Hub (ACH), is linked here. Showcasing how the project's digital tools foster knowledge sharing and educates users on how to interpret and use climate data is essential for this section, as bridging the gap between science, policy, and engagement is vital for effective climate action. The ACH is described here, showcasing the various tools and resources the platform provides. Fostering discussion among project followers through the ACH is also showcased, as the project followers are essential additions to the project. A video detailing the importance of *Adaptation AGORA* followers is then linked.

The theme ends with a discussion on climate disinformation, and how it undermines climate action. This is significant to the topic, as disinformation has increased across sectors with the advancement in technology and rise of social media. Disinformation is also another core aspect to many of the project outputs. With regards to climate data, disinformation can cause confusion among citizens and can mislead the public. Disinformation can also create distrust in science and climate data, which further harms engagement in climate action. Links to various IPCC reports are found throughout this section, to provide further information and to give credibility to the discussion.

The theme on Science and Data accurately showcases the variety and range of the *Adaptation AGORA project* and highlights the engagement of the project among the Pilot regions and project followers. The Digital Academies and ACH are properly highlighted here to exhibit the usability and application across science and data, engagement among project followers, and building media literacy to combat climate disinformation.

5.4 Public Awareness

The Public Awareness theme encompasses one of the main ambitions of the *Adaptation AGORA project*. The digital tools and many of the other project outputs were created specifically to raise awareness on climate adaptation and disinformation. This theme, therefore, is vital to the Handbook's accurate representation of the project.

The theme begins with establishing the importance of awareness in fostering action among individuals, tying the discussion back to the previous sections and creating an overall theme of climate adaptation and engagement prevalent throughout each of the themes. Public awareness is essential for effective climate adaptation in that it aids in managing climate impacts and reducing vulnerabilities. Building awareness also helps local authorities and communities adapt and respond to climate risks by equipping them with knowledge and information. Furthermore, awareness of climate change has also been linked to positive behavioural change and societal support in

adaptation and climate action. Greater public awareness occurs with the successful implementation of awareness campaigns, scientific communication, and education initiatives that provide the public with accurate and trustworthy information that allows them to make informed decisions.

Public awareness often culminates into a sense of shared responsibility and collective action. The domino effect described in this section ties back to the circle of the climate movement subsection in the Local Climate Adaptation and Citizen Engagement theme. This further showcases the interlinked nature of climate change, adaptation, and citizen engagement, both within those sectors and within the *Adaptation AGORA project*. The theme continues with highlighting capacity building within public awareness. Capacity building equips people with knowledge, resources and skills to understand climate change and fosters action. The video on capacity building within *Adaptation AGORA* is linked here. The various capacity building activities and tools are described, with links to resource publications on the *Adaptation AGORA* Zenodo community. A video interview on the peer-learning activities is also linked.

Capacity building is essential in raising public awareness. It equips people with the **knowledge, resources, and skills** needed to understand climate information and to take action. Capacity building goes farther than just providing information, it helps empower individuals, organizations, local governments, and whole communities to collaborate and build adaptation solutions that are best for their situation. Access to training, tools, and knowledge that make climate information relatable makes people more likely to engage, demand for solutions, and change behaviors. Capacity building also helps in bridging gaps of knowledge, especially for areas where climate impacts are great, but public understanding is limited due to the lack of resources and education. Capacity building is a long-term commitment, but one that will **build climate resilience from the ground up**.

Figure 13 Screenshot of the capacity building section and accompanying video within the Public Awareness theme

The theme then discusses communication and engagement within climate solutions. As public awareness highly depends on communication and engagement, this was a necessary discussion within this theme. Communication strategies within the *Adaptation AGORA project* are described, and a video interview on this topic is also linked. Various communication strategies, like type of

dialogue, understanding your audience, storytelling, and utilizing local actors, are highlighted here. However, communication goes beyond just talking to your audience. It also requires listening, engaging, and providing audiences a role within the solution. Communication strategies should also encompass workshops, town halls, and social media campaigns to foster discussion on climate adaptation.

Climate disinformation is also talked about in detail in this theme. As the other themes have highlighted the importance of the disinformation barrier to climate action, this theme dives into how to overcome disinformation as a barrier. This section begins by describing disinformation tactics, like cherry-picking climate data and using outdated sources or conspiracy theories. Media literacy is introduced here as a way to combat climate disinformation. Tactics to recognize climate disinformation are given, like fact-checking sources and paying attention to a sources' language and tone. Building media literacy among communities is essential to fighting disinformation. The theme ends with *Adaptation AGORA's Digital Academy on Climate Disinformation*, describing its use in fostering greater public awareness, combating climate disinformation, and increasing media literacy.

5.5 Policy in the Making

The final theme is named Policy in the Making. This theme was integral to the Digital Handbook, as one of the major WPs of the *Adaptation AGORA project* focused on creating a roadmap for climate policy. Policy is also at the core of climate action and adaptation solutions, and insights into climate policy are significant.

The theme begins with stating the importance of policy in combating climate change. Effective policy can help with the transition to more sustainable practices and can turn scientific research into laws, plans, and funding. Smart policy can also protect vulnerable populations. How policy is shaped is described within this theme, such as who is in power, what the public is demanding, and who is informing the policymakers. Understanding the barriers to policy is vital in overcoming them. Economics is also described as a huge factor in climate policy, as the impact of a green policy on the economy can dictate whether it is supported. Due to the influence economics has in climate policy, "just transitions" policies that aid in the shift to greener industries are heavily pushed by green policymakers. Lobbying and corporate influence can also be very influential in climate policy. Describing the various influences on policy is important in highlighting the significance of public awareness, as public opinion can sway leaders to act faster. Strong policy is said to have clear goals, establishes accountability, and helps ensure climate action is fair and effective. A video interview on participation in climate adaptation policies is linked here.

The theme ends with an overview of *Adaptation AGORA's* contributions to climate policy, most notably the climate policy white paper. This section showcases how the project has integrated citizen engagement into climate adaptation planning and policy. Further project analysis on policy and stakeholder engagement across the Pilot regions was done to gain an understanding of current

citizen participation within climate action. While current policy is enthusiastic, analysis revealed gaps, like a lack of accessibility and inclusion of vulnerable groups, and a shortage of participatory elements being implemented. From this analysis, recommendations on how to address these gaps and create more inclusive adaptation solutions that foster resilience from the ground up were built and the policy white paper was developed to address the critical gap between high-level ambition and on-the-ground implementation. The white paper also presents a strategic roadmap based on a comprehensive analysis of current research, policies, and practices, and builds on a synthesis of evidence from academic literature, EU policy instruments, EU-level documents, participatory practices, and empirical insights gathered throughout the *Adaptation AGORA project*. The policy white paper and a video interview on the policy white paper are linked here.

The white paper presents a **strategic roadmap** based on a comprehensive analysis of current research, policies, and practices. It builds on a synthesis of evidence from academic literature, EU policy instruments, EU-level documents, participatory practices, and empirical insights gathered throughout the Adaptation AGORA project. ([D4.5](#))

Figure 14 Screenshot of the policy white paper section and video-interview related to that within Policy in the Making theme

Strong policy is integral to having effective climate action. This theme details *Adaptation AGORA's* contributions to integrating engagement and scientific data within climate adaptation management and planning.

6. The four pilot regions

6.1 Introduction and narrative framework

To ensure a smooth yet engaging reading experience, a clear narrative framework, a distinct storytelling angle, was identified for each of the pilot regions. The editorial process progressed in parallel with the video editing work, allowing to weave together the voices of the protagonists captured in the interviews with the outcomes of the participatory and co-creation activities conducted in each pilot region.

This approach enabled the team to develop an interpretative lens for the adaptation journey of each of the four geographies, one that highlights both the uniqueness of their local contexts and the defining features that shaped how each corner of Europe has approached the challenge of climate adaptation, also in relation to their specific emerging issues and their social and cultural background.

This demonstrates that climate adaptation is a shared challenge across different latitudes. However, depending on the history of each place and its social and cultural context, both the specific challenges posed by a changing climate and the solutions communities develop to address them can differ significantly, as can their priorities.

The four pilot stories follow a consistent narrative framework to ensure coherent readability across the case studies and to reinforce the robustness of the structure featuring the common pathway the pilot regions underwent. Each story opens with an iconic image of the city accompanied by a concise, captivating statement that draws the reader in and conveys the central message of that narrative, the interpretative lens chosen to describe adaptation in that specific geographical context.

This introductory section, designed to immediately frame the perspective of the story, is followed by the pilot video. Unlike the individual interview clips, this longer video weaves together multiple contributions to portray the adaptation journey of each location. It brings together the voices of those who played an active role in the process, interspersed with contextual footage of the city and scenes from the participatory activities organised as part of the project. This combination provides a rich, multifaceted account of how each pilot region is responding to climate challenges. The narrative then continues with an analysis of the local context and the specific adaptation challenges faced by the city. This is followed by a dedicated section on stakeholders, highlighting the segments of society that took part in the co-creation activities within each pilot, ranging from local authorities and civil society organisations to representatives of the academic sector. Another section focuses on the climate-related impacts affecting each city and the resulting challenges and adaptation priorities identified at the local level. This is followed by a detailed description of the participatory process, illustrating how stakeholders were involved at different stages of co-development and co-creation. The section outlines the sequence of activities, from the inception workshop, through focus groups, to the final co-creation workshop, showcasing how the collaborative pathway

unfolded. The pilot narrative concludes with a section presenting the main results achieved, particularly the soft adaptation solutions identified through the participatory process. This final part reflects the collective insights and contributions gathered across the engagement activities, marking the culmination of the pilot’s adaptation journey.

Pilot regions

From the four corners of Europe: Italy, Germany, Sweden, and Spain, come powerful stories of climate adaptation, told through the voices of those living it.

Figure 15 Screenshot of the “hero section” of the Pilot regions webpage

6.2 Italy – City of Rome

For the city of Rome, the narrative was intentionally crafted around a central question: *Can the Eternal City—long celebrated for its resilience through centuries—rise once again, this time to confront the accelerating challenge of climate change?* This framing (Fig. 16) allowed the story to connect Rome’s unique historical identity with its modern vulnerabilities, positioning climate adaptation not only as a necessity, but also as an opportunity for renewal and social transformation. The chosen narrative angle highlights the contrast between Rome’s timeless heritage and the urgency of today’s climate pressures. Extreme heat, water scarcity, sudden intense rainfall, hydrogeological risks, and rising sea levels are presented as threats that intersect unevenly across the city’s diverse districts, exposing deep inequalities and differing levels of vulnerability. In this way, adaptation is portrayed not as a uniform process, but as a highly localised challenge that must

be addressed at the neighbourhood scale, where environmental, social, and economic factors overlap.

Italy - The Eternal Resilience

Rome has endured centuries of history, but today it faces a new trial: the relentless pressures of climate change. Can the eternal city rise once again, this time by turning crisis into opportunity?

Figure 16 Screenshot of the frame and video used for the Italian pilot area

The story also emphasises the city’s proactive response. Rather than portraying Rome as immobilised by its complexity or history, the narrative focuses on its strategic and participatory approach to adaptation, a pathway the city of Rome just started when the *Adaptation AGORA project* began. Scientific input from leading research institutes formed the basis of a robust draft of the first city adaptation strategy, which was then refined through a large-scale public consultation process supported by the *Adaptation AGORA project*. This culminated in the official adoption of Rome’s Adaptation Strategy in January 2025, an important milestone signalling political commitment and collective engagement.

By foregrounding both scientific evidence and community voices, the narrative underscores two key themes: adaptation as a pathway to modernisation and improved quality of life, and the need to tackle long-standing inequalities by focusing on Rome’s most exposed districts, particularly those affected by extreme heat or at risk from flooding. The large scale of the city indeed implies uneven and varied climate impacts over the different neighbourhoods, with higher criticalities in the Eastern

area, where the combination of built environment, anthropic pressure and lack of green areas increases the vulnerability of specific districts.

Water emerges as a symbolic and practical throughline in the narrative. Rome's ancient mastery of water, rooted in its aqueducts and abundant springs, is contrasted with today's mounting water-related challenges, from droughts to the need for more efficient reuse of treated water. This contrast reinforces the overarching message: Rome must once again innovate to secure its future. Overall, the narrative for Rome positions the city's adaptation journey as a bridge between its past and its aspirations for a more resilient, equitable, and liveable future, embracing climate adaptation not just as a defensive measure, but as a catalyst for transformation.

6.3 Sweden – City of Malmö

For Malmö, the narrative was deliberately framed around the city's transformation from an industrial hub to a modern, multicultural, and sustainability-oriented municipality, with a particular focus on the challenges posed by urban heat in a Nordic context, as a new and unexpected impact of climate change at such latitudes. The story compares Malmö's historical industrial legacy with its forward-looking vision, highlighting how climate adaptation intersects with social equity and inclusive urban planning.

The chosen narrative angle (Fig. 17) emphasizes vulnerability and resilience at the neighbourhood's level, using Rosengård, a low-income public housing area built during the Million Programme, as the lens for exploring climate risks. Heatwaves, a relatively new threat for Nordic societies accustomed to extreme cold, have uneven impacts across neighbourhoods, affecting vulnerable groups disproportionately. By focusing on this neighbourhood, the pilot highlights how climate adaptation must account for both social and environmental inequalities, demonstrating the importance of context-specific solutions. The case study on Rosengård, on paper meant to be a vulnerable neighbourhood, showed that adaptive capacities come from where they are less expected, thanks to the knowledge and the cohesion of a multicultural community used to deal with heat in their countries of origin.

Sweden - Keeping Malmö Cool

Nordic life is built for cold – bodies, homes, whole cities. But rising heat is a new, unexpected challenge changing everything.

Figure 17 Screenshot of the frame and video used for the Swedish pilot area

Citizen engagement emerges as the central theme of the narrative. From a past made of traditional top-down urban planning approaches in Sweden, where trust in public authorities has always been very high, Malmö has recently shifted towards a more democratic urban planning, involving residents, including marginalized and immigrant communities, in co-developing adaptation strategies. This participatory approach, led by the Municipality, not only identifies vulnerabilities but also leverages the community’s adaptive capacities, creating locally relevant solutions for heat resilience. The narrative positions Malmö as a model for combining scientific research, community knowledge, and inclusive governance to address emerging climate challenges.

By emphasizing both historical transformation and forward-looking adaptation, the narrative for Malmö tells a story of a city that has continuously reinvented itself, this time in response to climate change. The focus on heat vulnerability, equity, and citizen participation underscores Malmö’s innovative approach to adaptation: turning emerging risks into opportunities for inclusive, resilient, and socially just urban development.

6. 4 Germany – City of Dresden

For the city of Dresden, the narrative was structured around a key strategy that emerged strongly in this pilot region, also thanks to the presence of the WP2 leader among the German partners. This strategy centres on citizen and stakeholder engagement and is grounded in a simple but powerful

principle: active engagement requires going to where people are, meeting them in their own environments, rather than expecting them to take the first step.

As in the other pilot stories, the narrative (Fig. 18) begins with an iconic image of the city and a concise, evocative opening statement. In Dresden’s case: *“Citizen engagement is a challenging journey. But it becomes truly meaningful when we step into people’s spaces, listen to their voices, and meet them where they are—rather than expecting them to come to us.”*

Germany - Go where Citizens are

Citizen engagement is a challenging journey. But it becomes truly meaningful when we step into people’s spaces, listen to their voices, and meet them where they are, rather than expecting them to come to us.

Figure 18 Screenshot of the frame and video used for the German pilot area

Dresden is a city shaped by centuries of resilience. It has endured a succession of profound shocks: the great fire of 1491, Prussian bombings in 1760, the suppression of the 1849 constitutional uprisings, and most devastatingly, the Allied air raids of 1945, which left the city in ruins. After the Second World War, Dresden was rebuilt by faithfully restoring its original architectural identity. Its history is therefore already a story of reconstruction and recovery. Today, however, the city faces a new set of challenges linked to the impacts of climate change.

Dresden is increasingly exposed to rising temperatures, drier summers, wetter winters, and more frequent extreme weather events. Vulnerability is amplified by rapid urbanisation, population growth, and socio-demographic trends such as an ageing population. Densely built-up districts, in particular, suffer from the urban heat island effect, which intensifies overheating, increases health risks, and raises energy demand.

The narrative chosen for the Dresden pilot region emphasises the democratic dimension of participatory processes. It places citizens' experiences and voices at the centre, recognising them as essential to understanding local needs, vulnerabilities, and adaptation priorities. The city is indeed facing a significant rise in temperatures and increasingly frequent heatwaves, and it is adopting multiple approaches to protect residents.

Among these efforts, the HeatResilientCity project stands out, a transdisciplinary initiative exploring how densely populated areas such as Dresden-Gorbitz can be protected from extreme heat. Building on these foundations, the municipality is also developing a comprehensive Heat Protection Plan to safeguard public health.

Citizen participation plays a central role in these strategies. The pilot region highlighted the value of informal, practical tools, particularly digital applications, as enablers of everyday engagement. Examples include the thematic digital map available on the municipal website, showing public drinking water points, and a range of free mobile apps designed to support sustainable daily behaviours. Within this context, the *Adaptation AGORA mobile app* also found its place as another tool that meets people where they already are, online, thus creating accessible touchpoints with specific population groups.

Another important dimension that emerged in Dresden is the strong link between climate change, adaptation, and the healthcare sector. The health sector in Germany accounts for around 5% of national greenhouse gas emissions. For this reason, the municipal hospital is actively implementing emission reduction strategies while also developing adaptation measures, efforts that have been strengthened through its participation in *Adaptation AGORA*.

After an extended participatory process, the narrative of the Dresden pilot region is clear: citizen engagement is fundamental, because it is, at its core, a democratic act. Engaging citizens means giving voice to those who are often unheard, building networks that raise awareness, and promoting inclusive communication on climate adaptation solutions. Ultimately, it supports a more equitable and participatory approach to decision-making processes.

6.5 Spain – Aragon region

For the city of Zaragoza, and more broadly for the entire Aragón region, the narrative emerged as both natural and unavoidable from the outset. It centres on the relationship between urban and rural environments, exploring how these two very different ecosystems experience, respond to, and cope with the impacts of climate change.

In this pilot region, the participatory process involved citizens and stakeholders not only from the urban area of Zaragoza but also from the rural community of Matarraña. These workshops enabled an initial participatory diagnosis of the region's climate vulnerabilities, bringing together perspectives from both settings and highlighting their interconnectedness.

The narrative (Fig. 19) is encapsulated in the following statement: *“From villages to cities, every voice matters in climate adaptation. In Aragón, climate challenges and solutions bridge the countryside and urban settlements, reflecting the full diversity of our society.”*

Spain - Urban and Rural Adaptation

From villages to cities, every voice matters in climate adaptation. In Aragón, climate challenges and solutions from both dimensions bridge countryside and urban settlements, reflecting the full diversity of our society.

Figure 19 Screenshot of the frame and video used for the Spanish pilot area

This framing not only reflects the project’s commitment to inclusivity, one of the core pillars of *Adaptation AGORA*, but also emphasises the importance of understanding how two distinct ecosystems relate to one another. It sheds light on how they face both shared and unique climate challenges, and how different viewpoints contribute to identifying soft adaptation solutions appropriate to each context. It also allows for a deeper understanding of whether the issues are the same, how they differ, and how diverse perspectives can complement each other in finding effective responses.

In recent years, the Aragón region has been experiencing rising temperatures, prolonged droughts, and increasingly frequent wildfires. These environmental pressures are closely intertwined with significant social vulnerabilities. Low-income and elderly populations—whether in rural villages or in Zaragoza’s urban neighbourhoods—are disproportionately affected, often lacking adequate cooling systems, resilient infrastructure, or the financial capacity to implement adaptation measures.

Urban centres such as Zaragoza face additional stresses linked to the urban heat island effect, particularly in older and densely built districts. Social inequalities, including the limited availability of green spaces in lower-income neighbourhoods, further exacerbate these risks.

Despite these challenges, both the Government of Aragón and the Municipality of Zaragoza are taking action to strengthen awareness, combat climate-related disinformation, and advance adaptation efforts, with the ambition of making Zaragoza a climate-neutral city by 2030. The region is implementing several strategic policy frameworks, including the Aragón Climate Change Strategy. A flagship initiative is the Aragón Climate Week, a series of events organised in collaboration with institutions, civil society organisations, and private partners to promote adaptation and mitigation across the Aragonese society.

Furthermore, the co-design and co-creation activities carried out with citizens and local stakeholders through the project highlighted several priorities: the importance of climate awareness and education in schools; the need for more inclusive and accessible communication strategies; the value of climate shelters as safe and publicly accessible cooling spaces during heatwaves; and the relevance of policies that reinforce urban–rural connections.

The narrative developed for the Spanish pilot region makes it clear that climate change and climate adaptation are not solely environmental issues, they are also deeply social ones. The inclusion of diverse perspectives is essential not only to understand people’s needs but also to identify the most appropriate adaptation solutions. Ultimately, this framing highlights that addressing climate change is not only a matter of technical measures, but also of inclusion, fairness, and listening to communities.

7. Voices Section

7.1 The story told through the voices of those who made it

As previously introduced, the third navigation mode of Voices of Climate Adaptation invites users to explore the platform through the people, and the voices, who actively contributed to its creation and to the broader activities of the project (Fig. 20). This section is designed as a multimedia gallery where visitors can browse a curated collection of images and video interviews, many of which are also accessible throughout the thematic and regional pages of the site.

Voices

Meet the people behind the process, from project team members to local stakeholders, policymakers, institutions, NGOs, academics, and everyday citizens. Each voice offers a unique perspective, sharing their experiences, ideas, and contributions to shaping place-based adaptation journeys. Together, they bring to life the rich, collective effort driving local resilience across Europe.

Figure 20 Screenshot of the “Voices” section on the website

The gallery includes a series of filters that allow users to refine their search not only by content type, video or photo, but also by pilot region, making it possible to focus on the experiences, perspectives, and stories emerging from one region at a time. Through this feature, users can view interviews with stakeholders specifically connected to a chosen geographical area.

The guiding idea behind this section is to place people at the centre, to highlight their experiences, reflections, and contributions. Amplifying their voices was fundamental from the very beginning of *Adaptation AGORA*. The core purpose of the project has always been to bring civil society closer to local decision-making processes, fostering engagement and participation in shaping the future of their territories, and, ultimately, their everyday lives.

7.2 Interview process

Throughout the project’s implementation phase, a dedicated video maker accompanied the CMCC team (Task 6.2 leaders) to document the co-creation process and collect first-hand testimonies from stakeholders in each pilot region. Filming was carried out directly during the co-creation workshops, ensuring that interviews captured both the voices of participants and the context in which discussions and collaborative activities unfolded.

Interview sessions took place on the following dates and locations:

- **12 December 2024** – Rome

- **17 January 2025** – Rome
- **25 January 2025** – Malmö
- **4 February 2025** – Dresden
- **11 February 2025** – Zaragoza

To further enrich the narrative and gather additional reflections from project partners, a final set of interviews was recorded during the internal project meeting held in **Berlin** on **6–7 March 2025**. This final round helped consolidate insights after the main participatory activities had been completed. Prior to each workshop, the *Adaptation AGORA* team collaborated with local partners to identify and select the interviewees. For every location, interviews were conducted with both internal project members and a minimum of three external stakeholders participating in the activities. Interviews with internal team members focused on key aspects of their work in each pilot region: the stakeholders they engaged, the challenges and solutions emerging from participatory processes, and the climate adaptation needs identified by citizens and civil society. Internal interviews also explored the results achieved within each Work Package and the outcomes of the participatory activities carried out across the four pilots.

External stakeholders were invited to participate after being informed about the process and signing a consent form allowing the use of their image and recordings. Their interviews centred on their personal experience with *Adaptation AGORA*: how they first learned about the project, their feedback on the activities they took part in (including focus groups and co-creation workshops), and the impact that participation had on both their daily lives and their professional practice. In many cases, stakeholders were able to transfer the knowledge and skills developed through the project into their own institutional or professional environments. Several collaborations continued beyond the workshops, sometimes contributing directly to municipal climate adaptation efforts, for example, in the City of Rome.

The full list of interviewees, including their professional roles, institutional affiliation, and the corresponding interview questions, can be found in the Appendix C.

7.2.1 Italy – City of Rome

On 12 December 2025, an additional focus group was organised in Rome targeting stakeholders from the health sector. During the session, interviews were conducted with a retired paediatrician and a medical doctor from the Lazio Regional Epidemiology Department. They were invited to reflect on the focus group results and on how the best practices discussed could support their daily work, particularly in relation to the challenges and climate-related impacts affecting the health sector.

The relevance of the climate–health nexus also emerged in other pilots, notably in Dresden, where the climate manager of the municipal hospital explained how the healthcare sector both affects and

is affected by climate change, and outlined possible avenues to strengthen institutional adaptive capacity.

During the Rome co-creation workshop, the following internal project members were interviewed:

- **Paola Mercogliano (CMCC)** – Project Coordinator
Her interview provided an overview of *Adaptation AGORA*, its thematic focus, objectives, and long-term legacy.
- **Marina Mattera (CMCC)** – Project Manager
She explained the overall project structure and how *Adaptation AGORA* aligns with and contributes to the objectives of the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change. She also described the collaborations established with other EU-funded projects and the synergies developed across initiatives in the climate adaptation field.
- **Marta Ellena (CMCC)** – Researcher involved in WP2
Her interview focused on citizen participation, detailing the participatory processes carried out in Rome and the role of public engagement within WP2.
- **Alfredo Reder (CMCC)** – Researcher and WP5 Task Leader on Capacity Building
He discussed the capacity-building activities implemented under WP5 and the results achieved through training and knowledge-sharing actions.
- **Marianna Adinolfi (CMCC)** – Researcher and developer of the *Digital Academy on Climate Data, Risks and Tools*
She explained the academy's structure, objectives, and its contribution to enhancing community-level climate adaptation capacities.

In addition to health-sector stakeholders, a broader range of external actors were interviewed across the workshops:

- **Municipality of Rome:** an interview with Edoardo Zanchini, Director of the Climate Office, provided insights into the main climate challenges faced by the city, the barriers to implementing adaptation measures, and the municipal initiatives currently underway. A central topic was the public consultation process that led to the approval of Rome's first Climate Adaptation Strategy in January 2025, in which the *Adaptation AGORA* workshops played a key role. This makes the Municipality of Rome a strategic partner for the Italian pilot.
- **Public health institutions:** A representative from the Department of Epidemiology of Lazio region further described the complexity of managing public health risks in a warming climate, with particular emphasis on the growing threat of heatwaves in a city that must protect both residents and millions of annual visitors.

- **Academic institutions:** Representatives from Roma Tre University (Department of Architecture) offered a technical perspective on urban planning and stressed the added value of participatory approaches. They highlighted how co-design activities, such as those promoted through *Adaptation AGORA*, can help bridge long-standing gaps in territorial management and ensure that adaptation measures remain scientifically grounded and responsive to community needs.
- **Civil society organisations:** Interviews with youth and environmental associations, including WWF Italy and Fridays for Future Youth, provided the viewpoint of younger generations, who are increasingly active in climate advocacy. They emphasised the need for resilient living environments and the importance of involving citizens in the design of adaptation solutions.
- **Emergency response organisations:** The Italian Red Cross contributed expertise derived from managing climate-related emergencies, underlining the importance of preparedness and rapid response in protecting vulnerable groups during extreme events.
- **National institutions:** Finally, representatives from the Ministry of Environment and Energy Security described ongoing national-level efforts on climate adaptation and the relevance of coordinated governance across scales.

7.2.2 Sweden – city of Malmö

During the final co-creation workshop in Malmö, the following internal project members were interviewed:

- **Mathilda Englund (SEI)** – her interview provided an overview of the activities carried out in the Swedish pilot, the main themes and topics addressed in Sweden and the long-term impact on climate adaptation efforts in Sweden. *Adaptation AGORA*, its thematic focus, objectives, and long-term legacy.

Regarding external interviews, two adaptation strategists from the Municipality were interviewed. They reflected on their experience participating in the project’s participatory process, emphasising its relevance for climate adaptation planning. They discussed the specific challenges currently faced by Nordic populations and explained how engagement in such processes can inform and strengthen their daily work, as well as contribute to long-term resilience within their communities.

7.2.3 Germany – city of Dresden

During the final co-creation workshop in Dresden, the following internal project members were interviewed:

- **François Jost (ECSA), WP2 Leader** – His interview provided an overview of the activities implemented under WP2, illustrating how citizen and stakeholder engagement was

structured across the pilot regions and how the participatory process was designed and carried out in each of the four pilots.

- **Anna Verones (ECSA), focal point for the German pilot region** – Her interview focused on the activities undertaken in the German pilot, the key themes and challenges addressed, the region’s ongoing adaptation efforts, and the legacy and future prospects of the network established through the project.

Regarding external interviews, the following stakeholders were consulted:

- **Representative of the City Administration** – This interview highlighted the importance of citizen involvement in decision-making processes related to climate adaptation measures that directly affect local communities. The representative provided insights into the plans currently being implemented in Dresden to address heatwaves and strengthen urban resilience, including the *Dresden Heat Protection Plan* and the *Heat Resilient City* project.
- **Climate Manager of the Dresden Municipal Hospital** – The discussion focused on the role of the hospital in addressing the intersection between climate change and healthcare. Climate risks affecting hospital operations and the daily work of healthcare professionals were outlined, along with the adaptation strategies being implemented to respond to the increasing climate-related challenges in Dresden.
- **Representative of a private company developing digital tools for the Municipality** – The interview explored the benefits of digital applications for citizen engagement, detailing how such tools can promote behavioural changes and support more climate-conscious decision-making in daily life.

Representative from a civil society organisation (non-profit sector) – As a key collaborator in the organisation of workshops and project activities, perspectives were shared on citizen engagement and the promotion of inclusive participation. The discussion emphasised that such involvement is rooted in democratic values and is essential to ensure that marginalised groups are heard. Values such as inclusion, community participation, and network-building were highlighted as closely aligned with the project’s objectives.

7.2.4 Spain – city of Zaragoza

During the final co-creation workshop in Zaragoza, the following internal project members were interviewed:

- **Jorge Barba (Ibercivis Foundation)** – His interview focused on the *AGORA Quiz mobile app* and the importance of addressing disinformation as a core topic of the *Adaptation AGORA project*. He discussed the objectives, target audience, key features, and development process of the app, providing insights on how the project tackled this issue through the digital academy on climate disinformation, the mobile app itself, and related capacity-building activities and events.

- **Lucia Moreno (Ibercivis Foundation)** – She provided an overview of the main themes and topics addressed in the Spanish pilot, the activities carried out, and the stakeholders involved. Her interview highlighted the long-term impact of these actions on climate adaptation efforts in Aragón and discussed the primary climate change challenges faced by the region.
- **Judith Bielsa (Ibercivis Foundation)** – Her interview focused on the experience with the Matarraña community, explaining how the initiative started, how the community was engaged, the specific challenges of working with a rural community compared to an urban one, and the key climate change challenges identified in the region.

Regarding external interviews, the following stakeholders were consulted:

- **Representative from the Government of Aragón** – The interview emphasized the shared priorities between the *Adaptation AGORA project* and the regional government, particularly citizen participation and the fight against misinformation.
- **Zaragoza City Council** – The municipality expressed a clear ambition to become a resilient and climate-neutral city by 2030. Measures within the city’s adaptation plan were discussed, highlighting the connection with *Adaptation AGORA* through citizen engagement.
- **Representative from Academia (University of Zaragoza)** – This interview focused on the university’s commitment to remain engaged with society, promoting good governance and fostering proactive attitudes and openness to change.

Representative from Civil Society – From the perspective of social innovators, the main priority is placing people at the center of decision-making processes. The interview highlighted the importance of inclusion and the role of citizens as active agents of change.

7.2.5 General Assembly – Berlin

During the final General Assembly of the *Adaptation AGORA project*, held on 6–7 March 2025, a series of interviews were conducted with internal project members from all partner organisations, including SEI Oxford, UNIGE, IIASA, ATC, BSC, ICLEI, CIMA Foundation, and APRE. The interviews covered key activities, outputs, and experiences across the project:

- **Rosie Witton (SEI Oxford)** – The interview focused on the AGORA Community Hub, its development, main features and functionalities, objectives, and its role in facilitating networking, sharing experiences, best practices, and knowledge on climate change adaptation.
- **Enora Bruley (UNIGE)** – The discussion addressed the policy white paper developed within the project, as well as the review of policy instruments on adaptation. On the same topic, insights were also provided by **Dmitry Erokhin (IIASA)**.

- **Spyridoula Markou (ATC)** – The interview presented the Climate Disinformation Academy, a key digital tool within the ICT suite of the *Adaptation AGORA project*, including the main topics covered and the features of the academy.
- **Sam Pickard (BSC)** – The focus was on mapping citizen engagement initiatives and methodologies, reviewing existing engagement approaches, and explaining how this review informed project activities.
- **Benedetta Buccolini (ICLEI)** – The discussion provided an overview of peer-to-peer learning activities organised within WP5, emphasising the importance of sharing experiences and knowledge with other European projects.
- **Massimo Milelli (CIMA Foundation)** – The interview highlighted the relevance of scientific data in guiding adaptation processes and the role of clustering and networking activities within the project.
- **Francesca Santaniello (APRE)** – The focus was on project communication and outreach strategies, target audiences, and the channels used to engage them effectively.

7.3 Editing and Curation

The editing and curation process of the video material took place approximately from February–March until early September. This work was carried out by the project team in parallel with the editorial work on the written content. Video editing was managed collaboratively by the project team and the video maker, following a structured workflow:

The video maker first shared the raw footage, and each interview underwent a cutting process. Interviews were divided into multiple takes, each averaging around three minutes and focused on a specific topic, project output, result, or a relevant theme. Once the final cuts were approved, they were assembled with an opening sequence that mirrored the finalized homepage graphics. The graphic elements on the left side were color-coded according to the pilot region where the interview was filmed (Fig. 11), or, if the content related to general project themes, the graphics incorporated all four colours used on the homepage (Fig. 12). The opening sequence also included cover images of the cities where the interviews were conducted. The duration of this opening frame varied depending on the video type: shorter for individual interview clips and longer for the full pilot region presentation videos.

Figure 21 Screenshots of the opening screens of interviews conducted in Rome and Zaragoza, featuring graphic elements in magenta for Rome and yellow for Zaragoza.

Figure 22 Screenshot of the opening screen of a video related to thematic pages of the website

After completing the individual interview edits, the project team produced longer videos presenting each pilot region. These videos combined contributions from all participants to illustrate the local context, major climate challenges, approaches to addressing them, and key outcomes, results, and solutions. Each pilot region video followed a coherent narrative that highlighted its specific characteristics.

The process also included editorial decisions regarding the selection of cover images for the videos and the website, as well as the translation of all videos into English when originally recorded in another language for each pilot region.

8. Glossary section

The glossary section was developed to foster continued engagement and deepen users' education. By including a glossary on various important terms related to climate change, adaptation, engagement, and policy, Voices creates a truly immersive experience for users and improves the accessibility and flow of the platform. As users navigate throughout the handbook, they can directly

understand unknown or unfamiliar terms through the glossary connection. Terms are linked to the glossary throughout the handbook, creating continued engagement with the platform and sparking direct use of the section. The inclusion of a glossary within the handbook is significant, as a major barrier to climate change, adaptation, and policy is a lack of understanding, notably through jargon and language. The glossary section is, therefore, a way to bridge this gap and create a place of understanding within the platform where users can deepen their knowledge on the language of climate adaptation.

This section was built upon the glossary previously created by the *Adaptation AGORA project*, and more terms were added throughout the creation of the Digital Handbook. Terms within the handbook’s glossary include language that is typically seen in climate reports, scientific literature and project outputs. Feedback from project followers and event participants found a need for creating a glossary that explains common terms used in project outputs and events, notably the “co-” words. While the original glossary created by the *Adaptation AGORA project* is more expansive, the glossary within the Voices platform includes only words found throughout the various handbook sections. **Table 1** showcases the terms included in the handbook glossary. Links to the definitions and further information are included for each term within the glossary. This aspect further adds to the knowledge-sharing theme of the Voices platform and fosters further engagement among users to seek out other climate adaptation and engagement sites.

The glossary section serves as an accessible element of the Voices platform, providing further information and resources on terms that might not be familiar to all users and fostering continued engagement with both the handbook platform and with climate information overall.

Table 1 Terms included in the Digital Handbook Glossary

AR 5 or 6	Climate reconstructions	Co-explore	EURO-CORDEX	RCP 2.6	Multiethnic groups
Adaptation	Climate risks	Co-evaluation	GCM	RCP 4.5 & RCP 6.0	Media Literacy
Capacity Building	Climate services	Co-implementation	Impact	Resilience	Climate change disinformation
Citizen Engagement	CMIP5/CMIP6	Co-management	Interscalability	Risk	Fact-checking
Citizen Science	Co-assessment	Co-production	IPCC	SRES	Disinformation
Climate adaptation tools	Co-benefit	Community Engagement	Policy Frameworks	SSPs	EUCRA

Climate change	Co-creation	CORDEX	Public Awareness	Tipping Points	NASA
Climate index	Co-defined	Cost Analysis	RCM	WMO	NOAA
Climate projections	Co-develop	Disinformation	RCP	Vulnerable Communities	

9. About us section and Downloadable PDF Version

The final section in the website menu is dedicated to *About Us* and the project team. This section not only provides a general introduction to the *Adaptation AGORA project* but also serves as a hub for collecting all other project tools, giving them a life and legacy beyond the project itself. To present the project, this section includes both textual content and an interview with the project manager, Marina Mattera from CMCC. The tools presented in this section include:

AGORA Community Hub – A living digital environment, developed under WP3, enabling stakeholders, scientists, experts, media, and citizens to network, communicate, and connect with peers and communities across different geographical or societal contexts to share challenges and needs.

Digital Academy on Climate Data, Risks and Tools – Provides citizens and stakeholders access to open-source climate and risk data. Its aim is to increase understanding of climate topics among a broad, non-specialist audience and support practical strategies for effective climate adaptation. The Academy was developed under WP3.

Digital Academy Against Climate Change Disinformation – Equips users with reliable, fact-checked information. Through accessible resources and training, it strengthens the ability to identify disinformation, promotes climate literacy, and encourages evidence-based climate action. The Academy was developed under WP3.

Gamified Mobile App – Transforms climate change education into an engaging and interactive experience. With features like scoreboards and rankings, it motivates users to learn, participate, and inspire peers, while addressing climate disinformation and promoting sustainable behaviours. The mobile app was developed under WP2.

The section also introduces the coordinating partner, CMCC Foundation, the team responsible for the handbook’s development. CMCC Foundation is a non-profit research institution whose mission is to investigate and model the climate system and its interactions with society, providing reliable scientific results to support sustainable growth, environmental protection, and science-driven

adaptation and mitigation policies. CMCC's cross-disciplinary approach allows it to cover the full spectrum of climate research, including social, economic, and technological dimensions.

According to the Grant Agreement, the handbook materials were also required to be available as downloadable digital content, such as PDF documents. To fulfil this requirement, the project team developed a downloadable version of the website, designed as a scientific booklet that compiles not only the written content from the site, but also original images captured by the video maker. To make this product more engaging and suitable for quick reading, conceptual maps and visual graphics were added to highlight the main elements of the site and the project, including one for the project themes, two for the pilot regions and participatory approach and one for each pilot region. The complete downloadable PDF version is attached (Appendix D).

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Appendix A – Adaptation AGORA Digital Handbook User Interface Designs

AGORA Identity

Colours:

Font: **Poppins + Roboto**

Option 1

Editorial

1 - Moodboard

- blue text
- light background
- serif font
- stationery: notes, cards, folders

1 - Web reference

1 - Sketches

1A - UI design

Homepage

1A - UI design

Theme page 1

1A - UI design

Theme page 2

1B - UI design

Homepage

1B - UI design

Theme page 1

1B - UI design

Theme page 2

1 - Typeface

Voices of Climate Adaptation

Headlines Instrument Sans

Body text Crimson Pro

Option 2

Dynamic

2 - Moodboard

- gradients
- contemporary
- squared
- adaptive

2 - Web reference

2 - Sketches

2 - UI design

2 - UI design

Theme page 1

2 - UI design

Theme page 2

2 - Typeface

Voices of Climate Adaptation

Headlines **Poppins Semibold**

Body text **Instrument Sans**

Option 3

Immersive

3 - Moodboard

- colourful
- rounded corners
- light background
- rhythm
- full-screen images

3 - Web reference

3 - Sketches

3A - UI design

Homepage

3A - UI design

Theme page 1

3A - UI design

Climate Adaptation and Citizen Engagement

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore

Adaptation, a local and community affair

Charles Darwin considered adaptability the most important human skill. "It is not the strongest of the species that survives, nor the most intelligent that survives. It is the one that is most adaptable to change," he said.

When it comes to the impacts of a changing climate on society, adaptation confirms its key and specific role. While climate change is indeed a global issue, its impacts are very local. They are specific to a geographical area, may vary from region to region, and can be faced with different solutions, depending on the knowledge, on the background and the culture of the local communities who live in the affected area.

This important local feature of climate change reflects on adaptation. Adaptation, in human systems, is the process of adjustment to actual or

Theme page 2

3B - UI design

Voices of Climate Adaptation

A citizen engagement journey into local climate adaptation pathways across Europe

Funded by the European Union

Homepage

3B - UI design

Voices of Climate Adaptation | About | Themes | Hot Regions | People | Classes

Climate Adaptation and Citizen Engagement

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore

Theme page 1

3B - UI design

Theme page 2

3 - Typeface

 Voices of Climate Adaptation

Headlines **Poppins Semibold**

Body text **Roboto Flex**

Appendix B – Adaptation AGORA Digital Handbook Logo Proposals

AGORA Identity

Font: Poppins + Roboto

Option 1

Four arcs representing the four pilot projects. Font: Poppins

Option 2

Four arcs representing the four pilot projects. Font: Uncut Sans

Option 3

**Voices
of Climate
Adaptation**

No symbol, just a solid but detailed typeface. Font: PolySans Bulky

Option 4

Voices of Climate Adaptation[§]

§ A project by AGORA

The AGORA symbol is used as an asterisk. Warning: not legible at small sizes.

Comparison

A

B

C

Homepage design

Option A, with logo 1

[Interactive prototype](#)

Option A Linear gradients, plain colours. Font: Poppins + General sans

Option A Linear gradients, plain colours. Font: Poppins + General sans

Option A Linear gradients, plain colours. Font: Poppins + General sans

Option A Linear gradients, plain colours. Font: Poppins + General sans

Option B, with logo 2

[Interactive prototype](#)

Option B Linear gradients, plain colours. Font: Uncut Sans

Option B Linear gradients, plain colours. Font: Uncut Sans

Option B Linear gradients, plain colours. Font: Uncut Sans

Option B Linear gradients, plain colours. Font: Uncut Sans

Option C, with logo 3

[Interactive prototype ↗](#)

Option C Angular gradients, bright colours, ESA radar images. Font: PolySans + Uncut Sans

Option C Angular gradients, bright colours, ESA radar images. Font: PolySans + Uncut Sans

THEMES

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Climate
Adaptation
and Citizen
Engagement

Science
and Data

Public
Awareness

Policy in
the making

Option C Angular gradients, bright colours, ESA radar images. Font: PolySans + Uncut Sans

PILOT RESPONSE

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat.

[Explore >](#)

Italy
The Eternal Resilience

Sweden
Keeping Malmö Cool

Option C Angular gradients, bright colours, ESA radar images. Font: PolySans + Uncut Sans

Tuscany-Carlini Apennines in northern Italy. From Copernicus Sentinel-2 © ESA

PEOPLE

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[Know more >](#)

Appendix C – Adaptation AGORA Digital Handbook Interviews

Handbook_interviews at co-creation workshop in Rome 17 Jan 25

All interviews should be preferably held in English.

If a stakeholder has difficulties we can accommodate an interview in Italian.

Internal interviews:

- **Paola Mercogliano - Adaptation AGORA in general, purposes of the project, consortium, CMCC lead, main topics.**
Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in the Adaptation AGORA project.
Questions you might consider to address when recording the interview:
What is Adaptation Agora, and how does it aim to contribute to the global efforts on climate adaptation?
Could you highlight the main themes and topics that the project addresses?
What are the project's key objectives, and how do they translate into concrete actions? What results have been achieved so far, and what are the expectations for the final year of the project?
What is the envisioned legacy of Adaptation Agora, and how do you see its long-term impact on climate adaptation efforts?
How does the consortium's diversity of expertise support the project in tackling its challenges? As the project coordinator, what unique value does CMCC bring to Adaptation Agora?
- **Marina Mattera - EU Mission Adaptation, synergies with other projects.**
Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in the Adaptation AGORA project.
Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:
In the context of the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, how does Adaptation Agora align with or contribute to the Mission's objectives and goals?
How does Adaptation Agora collaborate with other European projects or initiatives in the field of climate adaptation, and what synergies have been identified so far?
How do you see the potential for scaling up Adaptation Agora's approach across Europe, and what role do partnerships with other projects or initiatives play in this?
- **Marta Ellena - Stakeholder engagement (added value of citizen participation to local climate adaptation processes) + Rome pilot.**
Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in the Adaptation AGORA project.
Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:
What is the value of citizens' participation in climate action and local adaptation processes? What are the methodologies and steps the Adaptation AGORA project undertook to involve citizens in the Rome pilot as in the other pilot regions?
What are the key achievements of this consultation process? Any relevant outcomes you would like to share? What are the most effective methodologies for engagement?
- **Alfredo Reder - capacity building, supporting awareness and education in the fields of climate change awareness and tackling climate disinformation.**
Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in the Adaptation AGORA project.

Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:

Why is capacity building important for climate action?

What strategies have been implemented to increase awareness about climate change among citizens and stakeholders?

What are the digital tools and resources (events/webinars) developed by the project to improve capacity building?

- **Marianna Adinolfi** - Academy on climate data - purposes, co-creation process, features, potential users.

Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in the Adaptation AGORA project.

Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:

What is the main goal of the Agora Digital Academy on Climate Data?

What are the primary objectives of the Academy, and which specific gaps in knowledge or skills does it aim to address for its users?

What types of learning materials, courses, or resources does the Academy provide to support its goals?

What types of learning modules are available, and what topics do they cover?

How does the academy contribute to fostering community-level climate adaptation actions?

External Interviews:

- **Edoardo Zanchini**
- **Other 2/3 stakeholders** from this list: Diana Giallonardo (DEMANIO), Marianna Ronchini (Ministero Ambiente e Sic. Energetica), Mani Bertrand (Coordinamento Nazionale delle Diaspore), Sara Vegni (A Sud), Lucia Raffa (Casa delle donne Lucha y Siesta), Valerio Renzoni/Mariagrazia Midulla (WWF Young - WWF), Rosario Marzullo (Enel)/Francesca Ciucci (Enel), Francesca de Donato (DEP Lazio), Andrea Filpa (Uniroma3).

Handbook_interviews at co-creation workshop in Malmö 28 Jan '25

All interviews should be preferably held in English.

If a stakeholder has difficulties we can accommodate an interview in Swedish.

For internal interviews: please remember not to mention WPs/tasks, any technical language should be avoided.

Try not to mention time/make time references, e.g. today, last month, next week etc. Try to think that these recordings will be used at the very end of the project to tell the project story, so they should be possibly neutral in terms of time/schedule of activities.

Internal interviews:

- **Mathilda Englund** - Adaptation AGORA in Sweden, purposes of the pilot activities, collaboration with local institutions, focus on heatwaves and vulnerable communities.

Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in the Adaptation AGORA project.

Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:

What does your organisation bring to the project in terms of expertise?

What are the activities you carried out in the Swedish pilot?

What are the main partners you involved in the project?

Could you highlight the main themes and topics that the project addressed in Sweden? Are there any special focuses? (heatwaves and vulnerable communities) What results have been achieved so far?

What is the envisioned legacy of Adaptation Agora, and how do you see its long-term impact on climate adaptation efforts in Sweden?

External interviews:

- **Ludwig Wahlund Sonesson** - Adaptation strategist at the city of Malmö. Collaboration with the Adaptation AGORA project, science-policy collaboration, focus on urban heat.

Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in your organisation.

Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:

How did the collaboration with Adaptation AGORA start?

What did you like about this experience?

Do you see any potential impacts on your day-to-day work?

How important is the science-policy collaboration in adaptation processes?

What are the main impacts of climate change locally? Focus on urban heat as a “new” challenge in Northern Europe.

- **Emanuel Toft** - Adaptation strategist at the city of Malmö. The importance of citizen engagement in local adaptation processes, focus on vulnerable communities/groups, the experience in Malmö.

Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in your organisation.

Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:

Why is citizen engagement so important in local adaptation processes? What are the benefits for the local institutions and for the communities?

Are citizens keen to be involved in those processes or did you find resistance? If this is the case, are there any specific groups more difficult to engage?

In the experience with the Adaptation AGORA project there was a focus on vulnerable groups? How did you reach out to them? Tell us more about the activities you carried out locally.

Handbook_interviews at co-creation workshop in Dresden 04 Feb '25

All interviews should be preferably held in English.

If a stakeholder has difficulties we can accommodate an interview in German.

For **internal interviews**: please remember not to mention WPs/tasks, any technical language should be avoided.

Try not to mention time/make time references, e.g. today, last month, next week etc. Try to think that these recordings will be used at the very end of the project to tell the project story, so they should be possibly neutral in terms of time/schedule of activities.

Internal interviews:

- **François Jost** - Adaptation AGORA in Germany, purposes of the pilot activities, as WP2 leader, an overview of the activities carried out in WP2 (without mentioning WP2), how the citizen engagement work was structured in the pilots, and the topics the German pilot mainly focused on, collaboration with local institutions of Dresden, focus on citizen participation.

Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in the Adaptation AGORA project.

Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:

Could you walk us through the activities carried out within WP2, highlighting key milestones and achievements? Also, could you explain the structure behind the citizen engagement process developed for the pilot activities?

Can you describe the collaboration between the Adaptation AGORA project and local institutions in Dresden? How did the city's administration and other local stakeholders contribute to the success of the pilot activities?

How has citizen engagement influenced the development of adaptation strategies in Dresden? How do you think the insights gained from citizen participation in the pilot could influence local policies on climate adaptation in Dresden?

Why is it so important the participation of citizens in the processes of tackling climate change adaptation and decision-making?

Could you highlight the main themes and topics that the project addressed in Germany? Are there any special focuses? (participatory city design - counter mapping of climate changes' impacts) Tell us more about the strategy you adopted to reach out to stakeholders "go where citizens are" approach.

- **Anna Verones, ECSA** - Adaptation AGORA in Germany, purposes of the pilot activities, focus on the themes of the workshop "enhancing the sense of community through mutual learning and education in schools" and impact on health sector.

Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in the Adaptation AGORA project.

Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:

Could you highlight the main themes and topics that the project addressed in German? Are there any special focuses? (impacts on health sector and theme of your breakout group “enhancing the sense of community through mutual learning and education in schools”)

How do you perceive the long-term impact of the project on climate adaptation efforts in Dresden and the surrounding region?

External interviews:

- **Marit Gronwald (representative of the city administration) - Heat protection plan - adaptation strategies at the city of Dresden, focus on urban heat, collaboration with the Adaptation AGORA project**

Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in your organisation.

Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:

How did the collaboration with Adaptation AGORA begin?

Why is citizen engagement so important in local adaptation processes?

Can you share insights into Dresden’s heat protection plan and the adaptation strategies currently being implemented? What are the emerging challenges and risks for public health in this context? What new challenges have emerged due to the impacts of climate change, and how do you think this experience can support the administration in addressing them?

Can you tell us more about the "HeatResilientCity" project and how your collaboration with Adaptation AGORA has influenced your approach or provided key insights to integrate into the project?

Useful

link:

https://www.dresden.de/de/rathaus/aktuelles/pressemitteilungen/2023/07/pm_054.php

- **Maria Binder - social/health sector. Focus on the importance of climate adaptation and heat resilience in the health sector; the difficulties of finding money to finance climate adaptation measures + the need to convince decision makers that these measures are a necessity**

Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in your organisation.

Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:

What has been your experience with the Adaptation AGORA project? Which topics addressed by the project are most relevant to your daily work?

Why is it important for a hospital like yours to be involved in engagement processes like this?

Why for a company of your sector is it important to be involved in these engagement processes? As a climate manager in a hospital, what are the biggest climate-related risks that a facility like yours may face?

What are the main challenges in securing funding for climate adaptation measures in the healthcare sector? How difficult is it to convince decision-makers that these measures are essential?

What new challenges are emerging in the healthcare sector due to the effects of climate change? How can a hospital actively implement and contribute to sustainability and climate adaptation strategies? Useful link: <https://www.klinikum-dresden.de/%C3%9Cber+uns/Das+Klinikum.html>

- **Tobias Gruber** – Sandstorm, development of Cleema app for the city of Dresden (<https://sandstorm.de/> , <https://www.cleema.app/>)
- **Christian Bärish** – The Internationale Gärten Dresden (<https://internationale-gaerten-dresden.de/>)

Handbook_interviews at co-creation workshop in Zaragoza 11 February 25

All interviews should be preferably held in English.

If a stakeholder has difficulties we can accommodate an interview in Spanish.

For **internal interviews**: please remember not to mention WPs/tasks, any technical language should be avoided.

Try not to mention time/make time references, e.g. today, last month, next week etc. Try to think that these recordings will be used at the very end of the project to tell the project story, so they should be possibly neutral in terms of time/schedule of activities.

Internal interviews:

- **Jorge Barba** - Fundación Ibercivis, Adaptation AGORA team
The importance of tackling disinformation as a main topic of the Adaptation AGORA project, objectives and development of the mobile app.
Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in the Adaptation AGORA project.
 Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:
 What is climate disinformation and why is it important to tackle it in a project like Adaptation AGORA?
 How did the project address this topic? (Academy + mobile app + capacity building)
 What is the mobile app? What are its objectives? How does it work? How was it developed? What is the target audience of the mobile app? When would it be available and where can it be found? (mention this from a retrospective point of view - like the app is available and can be downloaded from...)
- **Lucía Moreno** - Fundación Ibercivis, Adaptation AGORA team. The Spanish pilot, main topics addressed, process and stakeholders involved.
Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in the Adaptation AGORA project.
 Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:
 What does your organisation bring to the project in terms of expertise? Focus on citizen engagement.
 What are the activities you carried out in the Spanish pilot?
 What are the main partners you involved in the project?
 Could you highlight the main themes and topics that the project addressed in Spain? Are there any special focuses? (droughts and country/urban adaptation, please mention the experience with the Matarraña community)
 What results have been achieved so far?
 What is the envisioned legacy of Adaptation Agora, and how do you see its long-term impact on climate adaptation efforts in Aragon?

- **Judith Bielsa** - Fundación Ibercivis, Adaptation AGORA team. The Spanish pilot, main topics addressed, process and stakeholders involved.

Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in the Adaptation AGORA project.

Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:

Some of the previously unaddressed questions should be split into two sections if both Lucía and Judith are interviewed. We could ask Judith for more details about the experience with the Matarraña community—how the initiative started, how they engaged the community, the specific challenges they faced in involving this rural community compared to the urban one, and what they consider the main climate change challenges. Additionally, we could explore whether these challenges differ from those encountered in the city. Finally, we could ask about the legacy of Adaptation AGORA.

External interviews:

- **Marianna Martínez** - PHD. in Sociology. Project Manager. Specialist in Social Innovation, citizen, Design of futures, innovation labs, Gender, Agenda 2030, Smart City, Ecosystemic and connector. Process dynamizer.

Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in your organisation.

Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:

How did the collaboration with Adaptation AGORA start?

What did you like about this experience?

Do you see any potential impacts on your day to day work?

What are the main impacts of climate change locally?

What are your thoughts on the implementation of smart city solutions to enhance adaptation strategies and help communities cope with climate change challenges?

Do you think citizen engagement processes can help in implementing these solutions?

- **Paloma Ibarra** - University of Zaragoza. Professor of Physical Geography Director of the Sustainability and Agenda 2030 Secretariat, Department of Geography and Land Use and Planning. The importance of science-policy collaboration in local adaptation processes, how research can support planning and implementation.

Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in your organisation.

Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:

What has been your experience with the Adaptation AGORA project? Which topics addressed by the project are you most involved in?

Why is it important for academic institutions to be involved in engagement processes like this?

Do you think this type of participation can have a real impact on decision-making, knowledge transfer, and raising awareness among the population?

How much do you think is important the collaboration between science and policy in local adaptation processes and how research can support planning and implementation?

How is the university addressing the new challenges posed by climate change?

What key insights from this experience do you see as most relevant for advancing climate adaptation within the university setting?

- **Maria Luisa Campillos Apesteguia** - Oficina de Medio Ambiente, Acción Climática y Salud Pública - Environment, Climate Action and Public Health Office.

Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in your organisation.

Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:

What is Zaragoza city doing to address the impacts of climate change locally? What are the main effects of CC in the area of Zaragoza?

What does sustainability and strategic development mean for a city?

How did the collaboration with Adaptation AGORA start? What benefits did it bring to the city?

Why is citizen engagement important in local adaptation processes?

What new challenges have emerged due to the impacts of climate change, and how do you think this experience can support the administration in addressing them?

- **Raquel Giménez Acón** - Directora General de Educación Ambiental Gobierno de Aragón (Director General of Environmental Education Government of Aragón)

Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in your organisation.

Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:

What has your experience with the Adaptation AGORA project been and what aspects of this experience did you find most valuable?

What are the main strategies and policies adopted by the Aragón Region to address the impacts of climate change?

What are the key climate challenges specific to the Aragonese territory?

How important has the involvement of local stakeholders been in the climate adaptation process?

What tools and strategies has the regional government implemented to ensure effective citizen engagement?

What are the main challenges in securing funding for climate adaptation measures?

Are there any concrete actions the regional government is considering implementing based on the experiences and solutions discussed in the project?

What are the main lessons learned from participatory processes such as the co-creation workshops of Adaptation AGORA?

Handbook_interviews at GA in Berlin (march 6-7 2025)

All interviews should be held in English.

Please remember to always name the project as “Adaptation AGORA”.

Please remember not to mention WPs/tasks, any technical language should be avoided.

Try not to mention time/make time references, e.g. today, last month, next week etc. Try to think that these recordings will be used at the very end of the project to tell the project story, so they should be possibly neutral in terms of time/schedule of activities.

Interviews:

- **Rosie Witton, SEI Oxford - AGORA Community hub - objectives, how it was designed, how it works.**
Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in the Adaptation AGORA project.
 Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:
 What is the AGORA Community hub?
 How was it designed and built?
 What are the main features/functionalities?
 What users can find on the ACH and why should they sign-up?
 What is the competence/expertise your organisation is bringing to the project?
- **Enora Bruley, UNIGE - policy framework in the Adaptation AGORA project, enablers and barriers to co-creation and co-development processes, interviews with stakeholders, roadmap for transformational change (policy white paper).**
Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in your organisation.
 Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:
 Why is it important to have a policy review on the topic of adaptation?
 How did you carry it out? Which approach did you use? Which tools?
 What are the main enablers and barriers of the co-creation and co-development processes come out from the interviews with stakeholders?
 What are the main findings from the consultation with stakeholders?
 What is the main goal of the policy white paper? Can you tell us some insights from the document?
 What is the competence/expertise your organisation is bringing to the project?
- **Dmitry Erokhin, IIASA - review on policy instruments on adaptation, transferability of instruments and experiences.**
Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in your organisation.
 Questions you might consider to address when recording the interview:
 How was the review on policy instruments conducted? Tell us more about the methodology and focus.
 What are the main outcomes of this study?
 Review of digital participatory elements? Comparison between Germany and Spain.
 How did you evaluate the transferability of instruments and experiences from other policy areas?
 What are the main findings?
 What is the competence/expertise your organisation is bringing to the project?

- **Spyridoula Markou, ATC - The academy on disinformation.**
Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in the Adaptation AGORA project.
 Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:
 Why is the disinformation topic so important in the framework of the Adaptation AGORA project?
 What is the academy on disinformation? What are its main objectives?
 What are its main features/functionalities?
 How can it be used? (capacity building/awareness).
 What is the competence/expertise your organisation is bringing to the project?
- **Sam Pickard, BSC - the mapping of citizen engagement initiatives and of engagement methodologies.**
Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in your organisation.
 Questions you might consider addressing when recording the interview:
 How did you map other citizen engagement initiatives? Methodologies used and results.
 How did you review existing engagement methodologies? Tools and main findings.
 How was the analysis of capacity building resources conducted? How is this review used within the project?
 What is the competence/expertise your organisation is bringing to the project?
- **Benedetta Buccolini, ICLEI - the importance of sharing experiences with other European projects, pèer-to-peer learning activities.**
Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in your organisation.
 Questions you might consider to address when recording the interview:
 Why is peer-to-peer learning so important in the project?
 How do you reach out to other organisations/projects? What are the benefits of exchanging experiences and perspectives?
 What is the competence/skills your organisation is bringing to the project?
- **Massimo Milelli, CIMA - the role of clustering and networking activities in the project.**
Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in your organisation.
 Questions you might consider to address when recording the interview:
 Why is it important to have scientific data to drive adaptation paths/processes?
 How does science based information benefit societal transformation?
 What are the main objectives of clustering activities?
 Which are the projects/organisations Adaptation AGORA has been building synergies with? In which contexts?
 What are the outcomes of these activities?
 What is the competence/skills your organisation is bringing to the project?
- **Francesca Santaniello, APRE - communication and outreach in the Adaptation AGORA project.**
Standard introduction: Say hello, your name, surname and role in your organisation.
 Questions you might consider to address when recording the interview:
 Why is communication so important within the Adaptation AGORA project?
 What are the main target audiences and what are the channels you used to reach out to them?
 What kind of initiatives proved to be more effective for disseminating project results and findings?

What is the competence/skills your organisation is bringing to the project?

Appendix D – Adaptation AGORA Digital Handbook Downloadable Version

Voices of Climate Adaptation collects the results of **Adaptation AGORA**, a HORIZON Europe project, which supports the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change.

At the heart of the project are collaboration and community engagement. Citizens, civil society organizations, academics, experts, policymakers, and other stakeholders are involved in different geographies to co-design strategies to deal with local impacts of climate change. In this way the project delivers context-specific solutions, recognizing that there is no "one size fits all" in adaptation.

Who we are

The Voices of Climate Adaptation website has been created by **CMCC** within the Adaptation AGORA project.

Website content and curation:
Arianna Acciari, Antonella Mele, Madalene Baldell

This **downloadable pdf (long version)** has been curated by CMCC. Content and curation: Arianna Acciari, Antonella Mele, Emma D'Orto

Graphics and Infographics: Emma D'Orto

Graphic Design Layout: Antonella Mele

Image and video credits:
Renjagi Giorgi

Design and Development of the website:
Cinzia Bongino, Uplouse Studio

2

Oceanic phytoplankton around Gotland, Sweden (EUCC)

Themes

- Local Climate Adaptation and Citizen Engagement
- Science and Data
- Public Awareness
- Policy in the making

These themes offer a lens into the journey of adaptation that local communities and citizens are undertaking together to face the impacts of climate change. More than just a response, adaptation becomes an opportunity for collective growth, where science, policy, awareness, and active citizenship come together to shape resilient, empowered communities.

3

Local Climate Adaptation and Citizen Engagement

Charles Darwin considered adaptability the most important skill. "It is not the strongest of the species that survives, nor the most intelligent that survives. It is the one that is most adaptable to change," he said.

Adaptation, a local and community affair

Adaptability has been integral to life on Earth since the beginning. Throughout Earth's history, species have evolved and adapted to better survive their environment. In the short-term, we can see animals migrating to warmer climates in order to adapt to the changing seasons. Humanity must have the same spirit when it comes to dealing with the impacts of a changing climate, and adaptation plays a key and specific role in this.

Usually, climate change is talked about on a large-scale, with rising sea temperatures, extreme weather events, and melting ice caps. And while **climate change is indeed a global issue, its impacts can be felt at the most local levels.** Different regions experience different climate risks: some may face worsening floods while others experience crippling droughts. **This calls for diverse solutions that are tailored to the geographical, cultural, and social aspects of local communities.** This important **local feature of climate change**

reflects adaptation. Adaptation solutions can be tailor-made towards the different needs and vulnerabilities of a community. Adaptation, in human systems, is the process of adjustment to actual or expected climate and its effects, in order to moderate harm or exploit beneficial opportunities. For climate change, it can mean using hard adaptation measures, like building stronger storm defenses, rethinking how we use our land, or redesigning infrastructure. Soft adaptation initiatives focus on non-structural solutions, like utilizing native plants, implementing water management strategies, and using early warning systems. Adaptation is learning to live in a different way, in a different world, constantly adjusting to new challenges.

Adaptation has a lot to do with local needs and resources, with **territorial sustainable development plans, community thinking and collective action.** Each locality and com-

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munity has a set of specific needs and vulnerabilities when it comes to tackling climate change impacts. As such, adaptation has an intrinsic local component.

This is why **citizen engagement with adaptation is so important**. Applying adaptation solutions is about understanding how a community can change the way they live in their city, town or rural areas; the way they use information; the way they care for each segment of society, with a wide and inclusive approach. Understanding local climate impacts and barriers to climate adaptation can help with the ability of adaptation solutions to create meaningful impact.

Proper engagement within adaptation creates truly transformative climate adaptation and creates a feedback loop that promotes behavioral change. As engagement within climate adaptation goes up, climate solutions

become more effective and promote adaptation behaviours in citizens, which causes increased support for local, community-led adaptation. While engagement in adaptation is vital, many adaptation initiatives do not address critical issues within communities. **Citizen engagement in climate adaptation can help bring critical issues to light and influence decision-makers and policies** to address them within adaptation solutions. Citizen engagement is not only a democratic way to participate in decision making, but also a way to **make decisions more effectively** and direct the resources in a tailored way. To build meaningful citizen engagement, it is important to have clearly stated engagement objectives, involve a wide range of citizens, and tailor communication towards the specific audience involved. [1,2]

Along with citizen engagement, capacity building is also an important feature of adaptation. It is defined as "the process by which individuals or organizations obtain, improve, or retain the skills, knowledge, tools, equipment, or other resources to do their work competently" ([Climate Adapt](#)). Simply put, capacity building improves the ability of a person or organization to complete their objectives. In climate adaptation, capacity building initiatives can help build risk assessment and resilience, empower communities and support social justice, and foster collaboration and knowledge exchange that further strengthens adaptation solutions.

Raising awareness on climate change and adaptation solutions is key. However, the spread of climate disinformation can hinder this. Disinformation can distort the public's perception of climate change and its risks, can delay action, and affect people's trust in science and the policy process. Engaging people in ways that respect their communication preferences can promote more knowledge uptake,

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and supporting local voices and organizations can help provide respected, trusted, and accurate knowledge that is locally relevant.

Meaningful adaptation is not possible without public understanding and public awareness cannot flourish if it is clouded by disinformation. This is why engagement and capacity building go hand in hand when building climate adaptation initiatives, and why it is a major aspect of the Adaptation AGORA Project.

Climate change can feel like a complex and impossible problem, but adaptation provides us with solutions to not only live with the effects of climate change, but lessen these impacts as well.

A holistic approach to adaptation

Addressing the complex challenge of climate adaptation demands more than just technical solutions. It requires bridging disciplines and integrating diverse forms of knowledge. While climate science provides essential insights into environmental risks and future scenarios, it's social science that helps us understand how those risks are experienced, perceived, and managed by people and communities. Adaptation measures don't exist in a vacuum; they unfold in real-world contexts shaped by social norms, economic inequality, political systems, cultural values, and individual behaviors. If we ignore these factors, we risk creating maladaptation, when well-intentioned solutions unintentionally increase vulnerability or create new risks. For instance, installing green infrastructure without ensuring equitable access can widen social gaps rather than reduce them. Social science helps us ask the right

questions: Who benefits from this solution? Who is left out? What power dynamics are at play? How do we build trust and legitimacy in climate decision-making? These questions are critical for designing adaptation strategies that are not only effective on paper but also practical, inclusive, and just in practice. Moreover, integrating community knowledge, lived experience, and local values alongside scientific data fosters stronger public engagement and ownership, which are essential for long-term resilience. **Interdisciplinary collaboration**, between engineers, climate scientists, urban planners, sociologists, and community organizers, transforms adaptation from a technical fix into a **collective process of social transformation**. Climate adaptation is not just about adjusting to impacts, it's about **reshaping how we live together in a changing world**.

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A EU Mission to support local adaptation

The [EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change](#) focuses on supporting EU regions, cities and local authorities in their efforts to build resilience against the impacts of climate change. The Mission was born to complement climate mitigation and address the unavoidable effects of a warmer climate and to drive local communities to be better prepared to cope with these effects. The Mission aims to accompany at least 150 communities to climate resilience, through understanding climate risks, developing pathways for preparation, and implementing innovative solutions by 2030.

The EU regions and cities play a key role in the Mission, as the frontrunners finding and experimenting innovative solutions to local challenges and needs. Regional and local authorities that share the ambitions of the Mission can sign the Mission Charter to join. By doing so, they express their willingness to cooperate, mobilise resources and develop activities in their respective areas and communities to reach their adaptation goals. The number of signatories of the Charter already overcame 300 regional and local authorities.

The Mission funds various projects that focus on adaptation, like the [Adaptation AGORA Project](#). Efforts from the EU Mission on Adaptation have produced a wide variety of adaptation tools and resources that address various aspects of climate adaptation, like capacity building, citizen engagement, and case studies that highlight successful adaptation solutions. For example, the [Regional Adaptation Support Tool \(RAST\)](#) supports local and regional authorities with climate adaptation strategies. The tool guides users through the adaptation process, starting with development and ending with monitoring and evaluation. Within the Adaptation AGORA Project, the RAST tool was used in various adaptation and engagement activities (D5.1). Along with the RAST Tool, the EU Mission also provides [do-it-yourself RAST manuals](#) for citizen engagement that explain what participation tools to use with each of the RAST Tool steps.

The EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change represents one of the many international efforts in Europe to address the climate crisis.

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Citizens do care about climate challenges

Climate change remains among the top three concerns of Europeans. An overwhelming majority support action across the EU to tackle the climate crisis and make Europe the first climate-neutral continent, according to the [latest Eurobarometer survey](#) by the European Commission.

Among the main results of the survey:

- European citizens identify climate change as the third most serious problem facing the world after poverty, hunger and lack of drinking water, and armed conflicts.
- 88% of respondents - and at least 70% in each Member State - agree that greenhouse gas emissions should be reduced to a minimum while offsetting the remaining emissions for a climate-neutral EU economy by 2050.
- More than nine in ten respondents (93%) have taken at least one specific action to fight climate change, most notably by reducing and recycling waste (70%) and cutting down on consumption of disposable items whenever possible (53%).

These data are encouraging and confirm the **importance of involving local communities** in climate action, as they show a high degree of care and commitment to the topic steadily in place in many European regions. Citizen support of climate solutions helps build community resilience and puts pressure on decision-makers to implement effective and widespread policy.

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From knowledge to action, the circle of climate movement

There is great power in individual action, but it can be difficult to know where to start. There are a few key elements to having meaningful and successful climate participation. First, you must have concrete knowledge of your area and what local climate impacts are most affecting your community. You can get informed by making sure you are getting accurate scientific information and data, through your local institutions, climate organizations, or credited climate resources, like the Adaptation AGORA Digital Academies. Being informed sets you up for providing the [most accurate insights](#) into adaptation solutions.

Once you have that knowledge, you can inform others, through volunteering, or even just by having conversations with your family, friends, and community members. Raising awareness among your community can [spark further participation](#), informing your community also means letting local policy and decision-makers know you're aware and ready to take action. This is one of the best ways to begin change.

After informing your community and local authorities, you can [participate in co-planning adaptation solutions and initiatives](#). Co-production means collaborating with researchers, policy and decision-makers, and the public to create comprehensive solutions. This step allows people from all sectors of a community to come together and provide information, insights, and personal knowledge that will create comprehensive adaptation solutions. [Co-production](#) feeds into the next step, decide. All the knowledge and data created during the previous steps helps create

site-informed decisions on the most effective adaptation solutions and policy decisions for a community.

[Meaningful climate participation begins with you!](#) Understanding the science and data of your area gives you the resources to build awareness in your community, engage in co-planning, and help build effective adaptation solutions and policies.

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Science and Data

"Without data, you're just another person with an opinion".
- W. Edwards Deming

From data to decisions

Science and policy are often treated like different worlds, but in order to have effective climate adaptation, it is essential that science and policy work hand in hand. Climate science often refers to critical insights gathered on changing weather patterns, sea level rise, ecosystem disruptions, and vulnerabilities across different sectors, like agriculture, water, health, and infrastructure.

Using climate science and data is essential for [creating effective and comprehensive climate policies that help build resilience, enhance public participation, and foster sustainable development](#). Science helps inform policy in two major ways: by providing data-driven insight, and identifying opportunities for adaptation. Policy then takes that scientific information and transforms it into actionable frameworks. Without policy, scientific data would remain in reports instead of being applied in real-world action.

Data-driven policy helps governments and institutions use resources effectively, measure impact, and avoid unnecessary costs. When policy decisions are based on scientific data, it becomes more transparent, accountable, and responsive to the people and communities' needs. The [connection between science](#)

and policy ensures that [future decisions about adaptation are informed by the best available data](#), which helps communities respond to climate risks. Linking science and policy [also helps build public trust](#). It shows that the decisions made are guided by what works and turns good intentions into [effective action](#).

Despite the importance of science in decision-making, scientific knowledge is not always easily accessible or understandable for policy makers and the general public. Bridging this gap requires [continuous dialogue and mutual understanding](#). This is why science-policy interfaces, like the IPCC, are so important. They help translate complex scientific data into concrete actions for communities.

The Adaptation AGORA Project also attempts to bridge this gap, by providing multiple avenues for people, governments, and decision-makers to access easily understandable climate information. To have truly impactful climate adaptation, a key factor is science-policy collaboration. It is how we move from knowing the impacts of climate change to actually doing something about them.

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One of the main ways Adaptation AGORA directly addresses the gap between science and policy is through the Digital Academies. In the [Academy on Climate Data Risks & Tips](#), interested users can find accurate and easy to understand climate information on a range of topics, like adaptation, citizen science, and climate justice. The Academies go a step beyond simply providing information. These digital platforms provide a [truly individualized experience](#), as you can curate the platform for your personal use. Whether you need to find climate information specific to your area, you want to take modules to grow your climate knowledge, or you want to share climate facts, the Digital Academies provide the space for you to do so. Truly transformative change means collaborating and expanding climate knowledge at all levels, and the Digital Academies take a step towards this goal.

[Climate adaptation strategy](#) by engaging with members from various sectors to identify critical vulnerabilities and areas to strengthen resilience.

In Zaragoza, Spain, [online workshops with different local communities](#) helped co-create a vulnerability report that integrated social, economic, and environmental factors.

These efforts help bridge the gap between science and policy, bringing members from both areas together to create strong and comprehensive climate action. The tool Adaptation AGORA has designed to facilitate these interactions is the [Agora Community Hub](#), a digital space within the weADAPT platform that connects stakeholders, scientists, policymakers, media, and citizens to share knowledge and collaborate on climate adaptation. It offers tools, case studies, and experiences that help local governments and communities identify peers, overcome challenges, and learn from ongoing implementation efforts, while fostering networking across regions and initiatives.

The Agora Community HUB is also a tool that enlarges the community of the project, allowing [followers](#) to join the discussion and share their experiences. Followers are other regions as well as associations, organizations and institutions that are involved in the process of adaptation to climate change. The followers' concept expands the project's community beyond the pilot areas, engaging more people across Europe. It allows followers to share their specific needs and benefit from the project's insights and results from the pilots, supporting adaptation efforts at a broader scale.

However, a major barrier in bridging the gap between science and policy is the spreading of disinformation.

Disinformation can confuse and mislead the public, creating distrust in science and climate data and ultimately decreasing people's willingness to participate in climate action.

[Disinformation greatly threatens climate action](#). It can [erode public support and trust in climate adaptation authorities and policies](#) that causes division and isolation, supporting adaptation efforts at a broader scale. By planting seeds of doubt and flooding people with false claims, disinformation slows down progress and makes it much harder to build support. While [experts clearly show the link between human activity and climate change](#), disinformation campaigns cast doubt over the expert consensus, exaggerate uncertainties, and promote false solutions that delay real action. It is, therefore, essential for accurate and credible climate information to be available to policy-makers and the general public to help fight disinformation and build effective climate adaptation policy and public awareness.

How climate disinformation undermines climate action

It has been well-documented that human activities bear responsibility for the madam-day climate change we are experiencing.

Pilot regions insights

In the Pilot regions of Rome (Italy), Dresden (Germany), Zaragoza (Spain), and Malmö (Sweden), the Adaptation AGORA Project has held various workshops, group sessions, and webinars that brought together the general public, city officials, academics, and stakeholders from sectors including urban planning, public health, biodiversity, industry and civil society. These events targeted different groups, like youth, elderly, and vulnerable populations, and collected local knowledge to help inform adaptation solutions for each of the Pilot regions.

The efforts of the Adaptation AGORA Project highlight the importance of community engagement within science and policy. For instance, in the Pilot region of Rome, Italy, Adaptation AGORA helped [co-design the city's](#)

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Public Awareness

"Only if we understand, will we care. Only if we care, will we help. Only if we help, shall all be saved"
 – Jane Goodall

From awareness to action

Climate change threatens to create a more unstable and dangerous present and future. We can see this through the increasing rate and intensity of storm events and weather extremes. This marks the **importance of climate change awareness**. Public awareness paves the way for managing climate impacts and reducing vulnerabilities. Building public awareness of climate change helps equip local authorities and communities with the knowledge and resources needed to adapt and respond to climate risks. Certain groups can be more vulnerable to the climate crisis than others, making climate change awareness vital for these groups to adapt.

Awareness of climate change can also lead to [changes in behavior and societal norms in adaptation measures](#). It helps people understand the causes, impacts, and urgency of climate change. By increasing public awareness, people can recognize how their daily choices, like driving a car instead of taking the bus, can contribute to greenhouse gas emissions. Having successful awareness campaigns, scientific communication, and education initiatives help supply people with accurate information that enable them to make informed decisions, and support adaptation policies and initiatives. As public awareness grows,

so does **the sense of shared responsibility and collective action**. Raising public awareness can increase enthusiasm. Climate change requires widespread participation from communities, governments, businesses, and individuals. When people are aware of the impact of climate change, they are more likely to demand stronger climate policies and more sustainable practices.

Capacity building is essential in raising public awareness. It equips people with the **knowledge, resources, and skills** needed to understand climate information and to take action. Capacity building goes further than just providing information. It helps empower individuals, organizations, local governments, and whole communities to collaborate and build adaptation solutions that are best for their situation. Access to training, tools, and knowledge that make climate information relatable makes people more likely to engage, demand for solutions, and change behaviors. Capacity building also helps in bridging gaps of knowledge, especially for areas where climate impacts are great, but public understanding is limited due to the lack of resources and education. Capacity building is a long-term commitment, but one that **will build climate resilience from the ground up**.

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In Adaptation AGORA, capacity building was heavily used throughout engagement activities. Building from other EU projects and from previous project activities, Adaptation AGORA compiled the best capacity building methods for successful engagement and maximized the potential of project events. For instance, storytelling was used throughout project workshops to connect with participants and to relay climate information in a more relatable and easy to understand way. The capacity building tools, methods, and resources gathered from other projects and from Adaptation AGORA events have been compiled into [various documents and resources](#), to help future projects, organizations, and communities apply capacity building methods to build public awareness and climate action.

Moreover, **all capacity building resources produced under the project are systematized in a set of one-pagers** which can be consulted as a catalogue. Peer-learning activities are also key to build strong networks and facilitate mutual exchange.

Communication and engagement at the heart of climate solutions

Raising public awareness can take many forms, and as everyone responds differently, using multiple communication styles and engagement strategies is the best way to raise awareness throughout a community. As part of the Adaptation AGORA Project, public communication and engagement is at the core of what we do. Throughout our project, we have held various public engagement events to understand and co-design adaptation initiatives that are tailored to specific communities.

When it comes to raising public awareness of climate change, how we talk about it can be just as important as what we say. Effective communication strategies bridge the gap between science and the general public. If the message is too technical, too negative, or too overwhelming, people may get confused or anxious, leading them to tune out the message altogether. This is why successful communication makes the message relatable, clear, and empowering.

Knowing your audience is one of the best ways to engage with your community. While some respond best to statistics, jargon-heavy facts, others may need information with more layman's terms. Not everyone connects with melting ice caps and extreme climate scenarios. Understanding your audience means connecting with their daily problems and concerns. Linking local impacts to climate change is a key way of engaging with your audience and connecting them to the climate crisis. **Amplifying trusted voices** can help bring credibility to your message. Local actors in the climate space make your movement reliable, and people are more likely to listen and engage.

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ge with someone they relate to. **Storytelling** can also be a power tool. Personal experiences bring reality to climate change and can create empathy among your audience.

Climate communication is not just about talking to your audience, it's about **listening, engaging, and giving communities a role within the solution**. Workshops, town halls, and social media campaigns are great ways to spark conversation about climate change. Continual dialogue builds trust, promotes local knowledge, and fosters collective action.

How to overcome the Disinformation barrier

One of the best ways to fight climate change is to spread information among communities. But what happens when this information gets twisted, reworded, or muffled by inaccurate sources? This is climate disinformation and it is designed to stall climate action. [Climate disinformation is a serious barrier in the climate fight](#). It causes doubt and distrust in science, weakened support for climate action, and can hinder policy and international action. The [IPCC AR6 report](#) shows that while evidence clearly links human activities to climate change, misguided efforts clouded by disinformation can lead to public polarization, which delays and corrupts climate action.

Now this is not to say you should blindly accept scientific information. Being skeptical is natural and a good thing to practice. It means that you consider all sources of information before coming to a conclusion. However, you'll find that arguments expressing [climate disinformation](#) typically use cherry-picked information or outdated sources to "win" their argument. This is not skepticism, it is ignoring the facts and spreading disinformation. Climate disinformation can take many forms, from hard denial and conspiracy theories to softer attempts at discrediting science, claims that climate change is not man-made or that the threat is not as bad as scientists say. Some will use cherry-picked statistics to try and discredit scientific evidence or misleading headlines to lessen the impact of climate change. Disinformation is often caused by [local actors, like political parties and mainstream media](#). This differs from country to country, from community to community. This is where media literacy comes in. With the rise of social media, disinformation is trickier than ever. It is easy to become

overwhelmed by all the differing information available. It is, therefore, important to be knowledgeable about disinformation and ways to combat it.

The best ways to [recognize climate disinformation](#):

- 1. Check your sources.** If your source references scientific institutions, peer-reviewed journals, and reputable news outlets, then you are good to go!
- 2. Pay attention to the language and tone.** If your source uses sensationalist language, exaggerations, and appeals to strong emotions, then it's best to fact-check it.
- 3. Fact-check.** It is important to make use of independent fact-checking websites available to help you verify claims. In Europe, the [EDMCQ](#) is a major independent fact-checking organization that provides numerous resources on disinformation and other topics. These disinformation bells are part of the [European capacity of media literacy](#). Media literacy encompasses all the technical, cognitive, social, civic, and creative capacities that allow citizens to access, have a critical understanding of the media, and interact with it. Building indi-

vidual and communal media literacy helps people break down disinformation, making them less likely to be affected by it. Greater public awareness also plays a vital role in fighting disinformation. As communities are more informed about climate change, they will be less likely to succumb to climate disinformation. Growing the capacity of individuals and communities makes the fight against disinformation that much more stronger.

To do our part in the fight against climate disinformation, the [Climate Change Disinformation Academy](#) produced by the Adaptation AGORA Project creates an online safe space for climate information and aims to build the awareness of users with reliable climate change information and fact-checked data from credible sources. The Academy focuses topics like media literacy to enhance users ability to identify disinformation and provides real-world examples of climate disinformation. The fight against disinformation is one of the biggest barriers to climate action, and platforms like the Climate Change Disinformation Academy are essential in building comprehensive public awareness.

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Policy in the making

"I have learned that the problems of others are the same as my own. Getting out of them all together is politics."
-Lorenzo Miani

Governing change

Combating climate change hinges on implementing effective policy. It is what turns good ideas and scientific research into laws, plans, and funding. Without strong climate policies in place, efforts to cut emissions or adapt to climate impacts often end up scattered, underfunded, or take too slow to make a real difference. Climate policies provide the structure and direction needed to drive meaningful, long-term change at the local, national, and global levels.

Good climate policy helps make the transition to more sustainable practices fair. Not everyone contributes to climate change equally and not everyone has access to the same resources to adapt. Smart policy can protect vulnerable communities, can ensure workers in high-emission industries aren't left behind, and hold big polluters accountable.

One policy, many influences

Climate policy is one of the best ways to combat climate change, as it is the primary way governments and institutions respond to climate risks. It includes the rules, strategies, and incentives that guide everything, from cutting emissions to protecting communities from climate disasters.

Climate policy is shaped by a variety of factors, a major one being science. **Science-based policies provide the most informed decisions, but exactly how that scientific information gets turned into action depends on who is in power, what the public is demanding, and who is informing the policymakers.** Many policymakers rely on climate data, research, and expert recommendations to understand the impacts of climate change and what actions are most critical, and organizations like the IPCC and state environmental agencies help set the global agenda. There are other factors that influence policy, like politics. **Who is in office and what their priorities are can influence climate action significantly.** Some governments make major strides and push ambitious green policies, while others delay climate initiatives due to

pressure from powerful industries or because climate action is not politically relevant. While climate change is a long-term issue, politics often has short-term visions.

Economics is another huge factor in climate policy. Job growth, long-term savings, and the creation of new industries can be major advantages for green policies. However, if implementing a green policy seems too expensive or threatens existing jobs, there can be major resistance. This is why many green policymakers push for "just transitions" policies, which help workers and communities shift to greener industries. **Corporate influence and lobbying** can also influence climate policy, both in positive and negative instances. Some businesses support climate action, and push for strong, science-based policies. Others, like those tied to fossil fuels industries, may try to delay or weaken climate laws to protect profits.

This highlights the importance of speaking up and why staying informed really matters, as **public opinion can sway leaders to act faster.** When enough people care about the climate movement and demand action, leaders take notice. Protests, petitions, voting, and participating in local climate action can shift the conversation and increase political will. Climate movements led by young people, Indigenous groups, scientists, and everyday citizens have already made a huge impact on shaping climate agendas globally.

Strong climate policy is what separates talk from action. It sets clear goals, creates accountability, and helps make sure climate solutions are fair and effective.

A climate policy, white paper

Community engagement in climate policy is of vital importance to the climate movement. The Adaptation AGORA Project has showcased new ways of immersing citizen engagement into adaptation planning and policy. Across the four Pilot regions, project efforts have demonstrated that **policies are not truly effective until they include local voices.** Project efforts have analyzed policy and stakeholder engagement across the Pilot regions, at the national and EU levels, to gain an understanding of current citizen participation within climate action. Databases, reports, and other resources have been created to reflect our findings, looking at different elements like how many stakeholders are included, what participatory mechanisms are used and in what capacity? Are they private or public? Required or voluntary?

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All of this analysis helps us understand the current state of climate policy in Europe and can show where policies are falling short. What we have found is that while current climate policy is very enthusiastic, **there are still gaps, like a lack of accessibility and inclusion of vulnerable groups, and a shortage of participatory elements** being implemented. Many municipalities were found to have **inadequate human and financial resources** to effectively engage with stakeholders and communities were seen to have a lack of awareness and motivation to participate in climate action.

From our findings, we are able to build **recommendations to create more inclusive adaptation solutions** that foster resilience from the ground up. Gaining and deeper understanding how people are most affected, which communities are most at risk, and which groups are underrepresented helps build comprehensive climate action that will address the needs of the **entire community.**

Within the **Adaptation AGORA project**, a **policy white paper** was developed to address the critical gap between high-level ambitions and on-the-ground implementation. It argues that, to move from isolated successes to a new standard of climate governance, **Europe must adopt a holistic approach to scaling engagement.**

The white paper presents a **strategic road-map** based on a comprehensive analysis of current research, policies, and practices. It builds on a synthesis of evidence from academic literature, EU policy instruments, EU-level documents, participatory practices, and empirical insights gathered throughout the Adaptation AGORA project.

Radar image of Catalan coasts in Spain, from Copernicus Sentinel-1/RESA

Pilot regions

From the four corners of Europe; Italy, Germany, Sweden, and Spain, come powerful stories of climate adaptation, told through the voices of those living it.

These inspiring experiences are the result of Adaptation AGORA's work across diverse regions, engaging local communities and a broader network of over 35 followers. Together, they're tackling place-based climate challenges and co-creating practical, inclusive solutions, designed to foster collaboration, share best practices, and raise awareness.

- Italy - The Eternal Resilience
- Sweden - Keeping Malmö Cool
- Spain - Urban and Rural Adaptation
- Germany - Go where Citizens are

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Four pilot regions

From the four corners of Europe come powerful stories of climate adaptation, told through the voices of those living it.

Common participatory pathway

Diverse territories converge into one shared approach shaped through dialogue, collaboration, and local experience.

Sweden

Keeping Malmö Cool

Nordic life is built for cold – coats, fumes, warm cities. But rising heat is a new, unexpected challenge changing everything. Yet a city's ability for adaptation often lies from hidden corners, places you would never expect to drive such change.

Germany

Go where Citizens are

Citizen engagement is a challenging journey. But in Dresden, it became truly meaningful when we stepped into people's spaces, listened to their voices, and met them where they are, rather than expecting them to come to us.

Spain

Urban and Rural Adaptation

From villages to cities, every voice matters in climate adaptation. In Aragón, climate challenges and solutions from both dimensions bridge countryside and urban settlements, reflecting the full diversity of our society.

Italy

The Eternal Resilience

Rome has endured centuries of history, but today it faces a new trial: the relentless pressures of climate change. Can the eternal city rise once again, this time by turning crisis into opportunity?

Understanding the context

High participation in exploring the specific climate impacts – historical, trends, climate, and existing plans – ensuring overall city, local knowledge, and formal instruments. This report identifies where impacts are most significant and which communities, sectors, or ecosystems are most exposed.

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Engaging stakeholders

Workshops and consultations brought together a diverse range of stakeholders to explore the city's climate challenges. These included local residents, business, and local authorities, with building trust among actors. This engagement informed the city's understanding of the most significant climate risks and the resilience of our city's infrastructure.

Co-design solutions

Through a shared understanding of local climate challenges, stakeholders collectively developed strategies tailored to local conditions and their community needs. This process allowed participants to test ideas, compare options, and shape solutions that were not only technically sound but also feasible and meaningful for the people involved.

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Results

The pilot results are a set of **city adaptation measures** focused on reducing emissions, increasing resilience, and building new infrastructure. They are supported by **opportunities, actions, and measures** to ensure the **overall sustainability** of our cities and regions. These outcomes are supported by a **growing participatory, community-driven approach** to long-term climate resilience.

Italy - The Eternal Resilience

Rome has endured centuries of history, but today it faces a new trial: the relentless pressures of climate change. Can the eternal city rise once again, this time by turning crisis into opportunity?

Context

Rome, the Eternal City. A story unlike any other in the world: iconic, unique, steeped in history. For centuries, it has stood resilient in the face of time. But can it rise once again, this time to meet the challenge of climate change? Can adaptation become a springboard for modernisation and a chance to improve the quality of life for all who live and visit here?

Rome, like many major metropolitan areas, faces mounting climate pressures. **Heatwaves** are no longer the exception but the norm, stretching across **longer summers** and testing the limits of residents and tourists alike. **Managing water**, both when it's scarce and when it's overwhelming, is becoming increasingly complex. From **extreme weather**

events to the **fragile coastal areas**, and from the **protection of a diverse population** to the growing gaps between neighbourhoods, **the challenges are as varied as the city itself**. What affects one side of Rome might not affect another the same way. Some districts are far more vulnerable, and targeted action there is urgent.

But Rome, unlike its beautiful stone memories, is not standing still. The city has embarked on its **climate adaptation journey** with a dedicated local strategy. The first step was gathering solid **scientific input from top research institutes**, including the **CIACC**, coordinator of the Adaptation AGORA project. From there, the draft strategy was brought to life through a public participation process, supported by workshops and focus groups organized by the project. After hearing directly from the people of Rome, the **adaptation strategy** was fine-tuned and officially adopted by the City Assembly in January 2025.

The Municipality of Rome

Rome approved its first **Climate Adaptation Strategy in January 2025**, setting priorities, goals, and measures to prepare the city for increasingly frequent and intense climate impacts. This process matched perfectly with the progress of the Adaptation AGORA project, where the **Climate Office** of the Municipality, represented by its **Director, Edoardo Zucchini**, has been the **key partner in the Italian pilot**.

Stakeholders

This pilot case study convened a wide range of stakeholders, including representatives from civil society, academia, the private sector, and non-profit organizations, to address the **challenges outlined in the city's initial adaptation strategy**. The engagement process focused on **ten key areas**, from water management and urban infrastructure to cultural heritage, health, and biodiversity, pinpointing **where Rome is most at risk**. Stakeholders identified the city's main vulnerabilities and needs, while also highlighting ways to engage citizens as crucial partners in shaping a successful adaptation strategy.

Drafted in January 2024 after extensive research and scientific collaboration, the strategy went through months of **public consultation**, with workshops, local meetings, and citizen input helping shape the final plan. Adaptation AGORA workshops were part of this consultation process. **The strategy focuses on four urgent challenges: heavy rains and floods** threatening neighborhoods and infrastructures, **water shortages** from prolonged droughts, **rising urban heat** with health risks,

and coastal erosion worsened by storms and sea-level rise. The strategy outlines concrete adaptation measures, responsibilities, costs, and funding sources, along with a monitoring system and annual updates to keep citizens informed and engaged.

Other public authorities

The engagement process also involved **key public authorities**, including the **State Property Agency (Agenzia del Demanio)** and the **Lazio Regional Health Department (DEP Lazio)**. Their participation brought **crucial perspectives to the discussion tables**, enriching the debate with insights from their **specific areas of responsibility**.

The **State Property Agency** highlighted how **climate change directly affects public assets and infrastructure**, raising urgent questions about the resilience of state-owned buildings and the preservation of Italy's vast heritage. Meanwhile, **DEP Lazio shed light on the critical climate-health nexus**, stressing the challenges of managing public health risks in a changing climate. A particular focus was on the growing threat of heatwaves in Rome, a metropolis that must not only safeguard its residents but also protect the millions of visitors it welcomes each year. By sharing their sector-specific expertise, **these stakeholders helped connect climate impacts to tangible, real-world challenges**, from safeguarding cultural and economic assets to ensuring the health and safety of citizens, making them essential partners in shaping a comprehensive adaptation strategy.

Civil Society

Civil society associations played a vital role in the engagement process, bringing fresh energy, **diverse perspectives, and a strong**

sense of community ownership to the discussions. The **youth section of WWF Italy** and the **activists of Fridays for Future** reminded decision-makers of the **urgency of action**, amplifying the **voices of younger generations** who will live with the long-term consequences of climate change. The **Italian Red Cross** contributed its **experience in managing emergencies**, underlining the importance of **preparedness and rapid response in protecting vulnerable populations** during extreme events. Equally important was the **participation of migrant associations** representing Rome's multicultural communities, who emphasized the **need for inclusive strategies** that account for the diverse realities of those living in the city. Together, these groups helped **ensure that the adaptation strategy** was not only scientifically sound and institutionally robust, but also **socially just, inclusive, and rooted in the values of solidarity and collective resilience**.

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Academia

Academia also brought a crucial contribution to the engagement process, represented by the **University of Roma Tre**, and in particular its **Faculty of Architecture**. Their **expertise in urban planning** offered valuable insights into how the city's spaces can be **reimagined to withstand climate pressures while remaining livable and inclusive**. Beyond technical solutions, they stressed the **importance of involving citizens** in co-designing adaptation measures, **ensuring that urban transformation is both participatory and responsive to the real needs of communities**. By bridging scientific knowledge with practical urban strategies and citizen engagement, academia reinforced the idea that climate adaptation in Rome must be both evidence-based and deeply rooted in **civic participation**.

dating back to the Romans who built aqueducts to channel pristine water from the Apennines. But this long-standing advantage is under threat. Increasing droughts will make securing water supplies a top priority, requiring both investments in infrastructure and new approaches to reduce the use of drinking water, for example, by expanding the reuse of treated water, an area where the city is already investing heavily.

Rome also has **18 kilometers of coastline**, where **rising sea levels** are beginning to take a toll. The challenge is to **assess all these impacts**, across neighborhoods, infrastructures, and landscapes, and to use data, research, and scientific studies to **plan the city's transformation**. The goal is not only to make Rome resilient to climate change, but also to seize the opportunity to make it more modern, livable, and socially just, addressing long-standing inequalities in the process.

Challenges

In recent years, **Rome has been experiencing an acceleration of climate change impacts**, with **rising temperatures and shifting rainfall patterns** marked by long periods of **drought followed by sudden, intense downpours**. The city faces **serious hydrogeological risks**: rivers like the Tiber and the Aniene cut through its territory, leaving some neighborhoods highly exposed to flooding during heavy rains. This vulnerability is compounded by **past unauthorized construction** in areas that were never meant to be urbanized because of their proximity to rivers and flood risks.

Water management is another pressing issue. Rome has historically been blessed with an abundance of high-quality water, a legacy

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The greatest challenge lies at the neighborhood level. Public spaces need to be redesigned to be safer, cooler, and more welcoming, reducing climate risks while improving daily life for both residents and tourists. But Rome is a big and diverse city: depending on the area, temperature differences can reach 5-6°C between densely built-up, asphalt-heavy districts and those near large green areas or on the coast, where heat is naturally mitigated. **These uneven climate impacts overlap with social inequalities**, age, income, and other vulnerabilities, making some communities particularly at risk.

The city's Adaptation Strategy estimates that **around 9% of Rome's population is at risk during heatwaves**. Data clearly shows **where action is most urgent**: for instance, in the **eastern districts**, where green spaces are scarce. Here, environmental measures must go hand in hand with social, health, and communication strategies to protect and support the city's most vulnerable residents.

Participatory pathway

1. General structure

The project's four pilot areas served as testing grounds for inclusive, community-led climate adaptation. Starting in 2023, each area followed a **structured participatory pathway** an inception workshop to map key stakeholders, engage different target audiences and decision-makers, and identify local barriers and vulnerabilities; followed by focus groups with specific populations to better understand their concerns and unique perspectives; and culminating in a final co-creation workshop

aimed at developing actionable proposals and contributions to adaptation measures. The **emphasis was on soft adaptation measures**, non-structural, low-cost actions like public education and early warning systems, that address real community needs without heavy infrastructure.

In Rome, more than **100 stakeholders** from public institutions, civil society, academia, and business were identified and engaged throughout the process. This approach bridged community insights with policymaking, laying the foundation for long-term impact.

2. Inception workshop

November 2023: The process began with an **in-depth stakeholder mapping, identifying 42 key actors** across government, academia, civil society, and the private sector. This wasn't just about listing names. It was about ensuring diversity, gender balance, and inclusion of underrepresented voices from the start. The first big milestone was the organization of the **Inception workshop, where the 30 participants mapped out vulnerabilities and gaps in Rome's adaptive capacity**, setting the foundation for collective action. To maximize accessibility, the event was hosted in a venue chosen with public transport challenges in mind, and all materials were designed to be visually clear and easy to understand. Participants were divided into **small, interdisciplinary breakout groups** and guided through structured **discussions on climate vulnerabilities and adaptive capacity gaps across nine critical sectors** in line with the adaptation strategy of the city of Rome, from **water and infrastructure to health and cultural heritage**. Using infographics and color-coded post-its, participants mapped out both sector-specific and cross-cutting issues, while trained facilitators ensured balanced dialo-

gue. The workshop concluded with a **dynamic table-to-table feedback round**, allowing all groups to review and refine each other's contributions. This marked the **formal launch of the participatory pathway**, anchoring it in both inclusivity and collective ownership.

3. Focus groups

Summer and Autumn 2024: The second step shifted from exploration to dialogue through a series of thematic focus groups. **Workers, youth, multicultural communities, and health professionals**. Each group brought different lived experiences and perspectives, from everyday workplace challenges to youth activism, public health concerns, and traditional knowledge from migrant communities. The sessions combined open dialogue with **structured facilitation techniques** such as Think-Pair-Share, the Nominal Group Techni-

que, and 1-2-4-All. Participants first reflected on vulnerabilities and needs, then worked together to define **priority "soft" adaptation measures**, actions like awareness campaigns, education programs, or community-based early warning systems. A specially developed **Citizen Engagement Card Deck** helped participants evaluate which participatory methods (e.g. mentorship programs, citizen assemblies, peer-learning circles) could best support the implementation of the selected soft adaptation measures. This tool proved particularly effective in making the process accessible, even for participants unfamiliar with formal participatory mechanisms.

4. Co-creation workshop

January 2025: The final step brought the process full circle with the co-creation workshop, which took place in **January 2025, just as the City of Rome officially adopted its first Climate Adaptation Strategy**. The timing underscored how the participatory pathway had actively supported the city throughout the strategy's development, creating direct links between institutional planning and citizen-driven contributions. A total of **44 participants** came together to transform the priorities identified in earlier phases into concrete adaptation proposals. Working in **six breakout groups supported by facilitators**, participants revisited earlier findings on **vulnerabilities and adaptive capacity gaps, then refined them into actionable measures**. A dedicated set of visual cards and infographics synthesized the outputs from the focus groups, serving as prompts to guide discussion. Each group was asked to classify proposals into thematic domains such as commu-

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nition, education, or both, ensuring clarity and coherence. Alongside these impact-related criteria, **participants also assessed the practical feasibility of each approach**, considering factors such as implementation costs, logistical accessibility, required skills, and the availability of institutional support. Following the group-based assessment, a final plenary discussion provided space for each group to present its insights and recommendations. The integration of tailored facilitation techniques, structured visual tools, and thematically focused prompts across all phases of the process ensured that each session yielded two interrelated outcomes: a shortlist of soft adaptation measures and a corresponding set of preferred engagement strategies to support their implementation.

By the end of the workshop, **participants had produced a set of tangible, socially oriented adaptation actions**, grounded in both scientific evidence and community experience. The workshop thus represented the culmination

of the participatory journey: from mapping and listening to co-designing strategies that complemented and reinforced Rome's newly adopted adaptation strategy, helping to ensure it is not only a technical document, but a living, inclusive, and community-owned pathway toward resilience. For more detailed information on the workshop, you can consult the [dedicated report](#).

Participation was the key topic of a [dedicated webinar of the peer-to-peer learning series](#). Participatory experiences were discussed involving also the Adaptation AGORA's follower Ftial venoda Giulia Region.

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Results

Education and community at the heart of climate adaptation

The engagement process in Rome showed a clear priority: **education and community awareness are the cornerstones of climate adaptation**. Participants agreed that schools, communities, and public spaces should be at the center of change.

A key proposal was to **embed climate education in school curricula**, supported by practical, locally relevant activities like workshops and field trips. This was seen as a long-term investment in future generations, enabling young people to become climate advocates within their families and communities. Beyond schools, participants stressed the **importance of awareness-raising initiatives**, from public events and campaigns to neighborhood consultations. When paired with affective communication, these activities were seen as essential for mobilizing broad participation. Other promising ideas included **collaborative mentoring programs**, to foster bottom-up involvement and ownership of adaptation strategies, and **community skill-building workshops**, especially in schools, offering low-cost, high-impact ways to strengthen local resilience.

Across all discussions, the reasons behind the preferences became clear:

- **Long-term impact:** school programs seen as investments in future generations.
- **Inclusivity and accessibility:** public events and consultations valued for their ability to involve diverse groups.
- **Adaptability:** mentoring and community workshops praised for tailoring solutions to local needs.
- **Feasibility:** preference for approaches that

build on existing infrastructure (schools, public spaces) to minimize costs and maximize reach.

Participants co-created a **final package of "soft" adaptation measures** centred on **education, awareness, and community engagement**. This mix was considered the most effective pathway to strengthen Rome's collective capacity to face climate change, combining the energy of youth, the inclusivity of public events, and the ownership fostered by participatory approaches.

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Italy's pathway Rome

The Eternal Resilience

Rome, the Eternal City, for centuries, it has stood resilient in the face of fires, but can it rise once again, this time to meet the challenge of climate change? Can adaptation become a springboard for innovation and a driver to improve the quality of life for all who live and visit here? Unlike its beautiful stone monuments, Rome is not standing still, but it has embarked on its climate adaptation journey with a dedicated local strategy.

LOCAL IMPACTS

- Rising sea level
- Shifting rainfall patterns
- Rising temperatures

VULNERABILITIES

- 18 Km of coastline
- 3 rivers: Tiber and its affluents Arno and Almona
- 5-6 °C temperature rise
- 9% of population at risk

RISKS & CHALLENGES

- Floods
- Heatwaves
- Water management
- Coastal erosion
- Longer summers

More than 100 **STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED**, from 4 key groups.

Municipality

Other public authorities

Civil society

Academia

PARTICIPATORY PATHWAY

RESULTS

Sweden - Keeping Malmö cool

Nordic life is built for cold — bodies, homes, whole cities. But rising heat is a new, unexpected challenge changing everything.

Context

Malmö is a **modern, multicultural city** in Southern Sweden, overlooking the Öresund strait, as a maritime crossroads in the Baltic Sea. Connected to Denmark by the longest bridge combined with a tunnel in Europe, its cutting-edge design and growing technology sector define the new face of a city with an important industrial past. **In the late 1970s, Malmö faced a major recession** that hit its

once-strong shipbuilding and manufacturing industries hard. When the city's largest employer shut down in 1985, unemployment surged and many middle-class families left the city. By 1986, Malmö had lost around 35,000 residents. The crisis deepened through the '80s and '90s. This marked a turning point: Malmö could no longer rely on heavy industry and began **reinventing itself as a hub for**

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culture, design and technology. Over the past 15 years, Malmö's leaders have carefully crafted a long-term vision to blend its medieval heritage with modern, sustainable architecture. The result is a vibrant city of minimalist design, historic charm, green spaces, and popular beaches. Urban planners from around the world now look to Malmö for inspiration on how to successfully combine tradition, innovation, and sustainability. The "Turning Torso" skyscraper by Calatrava is the symbol of Malmö's new life.

The case study of the research in Malmö was Rosengård, a low-income public housing neighborhood built between the end of '60s and the beginning of '70s in the framework of the Miljon programme, a large-scale public housing project, aimed to provide affordable and modern housing to the growing urban population.

The research began with the assumption that this neighborhood, home to many residents from outside Sweden, would reveal both significant vulnerabilities and strong adaptive capacities.

preparing its infrastructure for harsh winters. However, with rising temperatures and the growing impact of urban heat islands, the city is **now turning its attention to heat vulnerability**. The municipality is actively exploring how to integrate heat resilience into urban planning, ensuring that new buildings are designed to withstand higher temperatures and that existing structures can be adapted to meet the emerging challenges. Their goal is to embed heat considerations into the upcoming city plan, with a strong emphasis on protecting vulnerable populations.

The Public Housing Company MKB

A key local partner in the project was the public housing company, a relevant player in Sweden where **the responsibility for climate adaptation lies with property owners**. With their broad mandate and deep local presence, they were an ideal collaborator. The research protocol was co-designed with the

Stakeholders

This pilot case study brought together a diverse group of stakeholders, from civil society and academia to the private sector and non-profit organizations, to tackle the growing threat of heatwaves in urban areas. At its core, the study focused on how extreme heat impacts the city's most vulnerable residents, aiming to drive inclusive and informed solutions.

The Municipality of Malmö

Historically, the city of Malmö has focused on

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cal partner and the Adaptation AGORA team shadowed their community officer, and went door-to-door, speaking with residents to gather firsthand insights into their perceptions and experiences.

Challenges

Nordic countries and Nordic people are used to dealing with extreme cold. Their bodies, the buildings they live in, their cities are prepared for cold. Heat in the Nordics is a recent effect of climate change that local communities were not expecting to face. A challenge to the way Nordic societies have been living so far. This is why **urban heat vulnerability**, with a focus on engaging vulnerable groups, **was the key research topic** of the Swedish pilot region. Heatwaves are more frequent and intense, with unequal impacts across neighborhoods and citizens.

Malmö is leading the way in tackling climate adaptation, setting itself apart by actively involving its citizens in shaping the city's strategies,

including vulnerable groups to shape a heat resilient city. This approach marks a significant shift in Sweden, where urban planning has traditionally followed a top-down, engineering-driven model, relying on strong public trust in institutions rather than public participation. Malmö's commitment to citizen engagement signals a bold and refreshing change.

Heat preparedness was the key topic of a [dedicated webinar of the peer-to-peer learning series](#). The Municipality of Malmö discussed their plans and actions with the Municipality of Valencia, one of the Adaptation AGORA's followers.

Participatory pathway

1. General structure

The project's four pilot areas served as testing grounds for inclusive, community-led climate adaptation. Starting in 2023, each area followed a **structured participatory pathway**:

an inception workshop to spark dialogue and map key stakeholders; focus groups to explore local vulnerabilities and co-design ideas; and a final co-creation workshop to refine solutions and chart implementation strategies. **The emphasis was on soft adaptation measures**, non-structural, low-cost actions like public education and early warning systems, that address real community needs without heavy infrastructure. In Malmö, **112 stakeholders** from public institutions, civil society, academia, and business were identified and engaged when kicking-off the inception workshop. This approach bridged community insights with policymaking, laying the foundation for long-term impact.

2. Inception workshop

September 2023: The project touched its first pilot activity in Malmö, Sweden, in September 2023 with a dynamic workshop bringing together stakeholders from diverse backgrounds. The focus: how to adapt to rising heatwaves, and who's most at risk. After a brief intro from the Stockholm Environment Institute on Adaptation AGORA and the EU Mission on Adaptation, participants split into groups to explore the meaning of climate vulnerability. Discussions zoomed in on the social and physical factors that shape how different communities experience extreme heat. Using academic research on at-risk groups, participants debated who is most vulnerable and why. Key themes included the need for intersectional approaches, systems thinking, and inclusive urban planning. This inception workshop laid the groundwork for the next phases.

3. Focus groups

Summer 2024: In Malmö, the standard path of focus groups was coupled with interviews

with residents living in the Rosengård neighbourhood to understand lived experiences of heatwaves. The interviews involved around 100 residents, collecting their views and perceptions on heat vulnerability. The focus groups involved **three key segments of Malmö's society: young people, workers, and multicultural communities**. In these sessions, participants didn't just share their perspectives, they actively shaped the path forward. Together, they assessed the most promising soft climate adaptation solutions and explored the most effective ways to engage their communities in putting those ideas into action. The goal: ensure solutions are not only smart but also practical, inclusive, and rooted in everyday realities.

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4. Co-creation workshop

The end of 2024 marked an important milestone for Malmö, where the municipality published a politically backed report based on Adaptation AGORA project findings, **"Extremvärme i Malmö: Vem drabbas och hur kan vi lindra effekterna?"** (Extreme Heat in Malmö: Who is Affected and How Can We Mitigate the Effects?). The co-authored report is available only in Swedish and explores urban heat vulnerability. The report positions Malmö as a great example, inspiring other cities to follow suit. In **January 2025**, BEI HQ and the City of Malmö hosted a vibrant **co-creation workshop focused on urban heat resilience**, collecting the inputs from the previous phases of the engagement path and bringing outcomes to future initiatives. **Nearly 40 participants** from across city departments came together to break silos and confront the growing risks of heatwaves. The City of Malmö used the event to launch a new working group dedicated to integrating heat mitigation into urban planning. Presentations from local experts and external voices explored key questions: Who is most affected by heat stress? What have we learned through Adaptation AGORA? How can cities plan for a better future?

Results

What We Learned from Listening: Heat, Trust, and Everyday Resilience

In Malmö's Rosengård, statistics might label the community as vulnerable, but reality is more complex. Residents cherish their neighborhood, enjoy the green spaces, and don't always see heat as a major concern, unless it's sweltering indoors. This revealed a key insight: **vulnerability is not just data, it's lived experience**, and citizen engagement is essential to uncovering it.

Across all four Adaptation AGORA pilot regions, different groups brought different needs and perspectives:

- **Youth** in Malmö preferred **reliable, decentralized communication** (like transit displays or radio alerts) over participatory methods, reflecting strong trust in public institutions.
- **Workers** favored **practical, low-effort** for-

mat, like in-situ sessions at workplaces or public alerts, highlighting a need for time-efficient, low-threshold engagement.

- **Multicultural communities** valued **culturally rooted formats**, such as storytelling, food, or art, making engagement feel personal and relatable.

- **Outdoor workers** leaned toward **passive tools like local alert systems** but remained skeptical of citizen-led initiatives, trusting formal institutions to lead in emergencies.

Educational approaches also mattered: **school-based, intergenerational learning and hands-on environmental education**, especially when embedded in everyday spaces, were seen as both effective and accessible. One common thread? **High institutional trust** shaped how people saw their role in climate adaptation. Many preferred that public authorities take the lead, as educators, pro-

fectors, and planners. Ultimately, the project experience confirmed **that effective climate engagement isn't one-size-fits-all. It must be context-aware, culturally resonant, and grounded in people's daily lives.**

Building on the strong foundation laid by Adaptation AGORA, the legacy of community-driven climate resilience lives on through the new HeatSafe project. Funded by Formas, HeatSafe brings together BEI HQ, the City of Malmö, Linköping University, and Imagine Adaptation (led by BC3) to deepen research and develop advanced decision-support tools, ensuring Malmö stays prepared and protected as heat risks rise. Thanks to the legacy of Adaptation AGORA, Malmö is not just staying cool in the face of rising temperatures, it's staying cool as a modern, forward-thinking city, ready and equipped to tackle new climate challenges with confidence and innovation.

An interactive session followed, where participants co-developed practical solutions and assigned responsibilities. The results focused on four key areas:

- 1. Nature-based solutions** - Expand and care for green spaces to cool the city equitably.
- 2. Indoor design strategies** - Boost thermal comfort with shading, insulation, and new cooling tech.
- 3. Knowledge exchange** - Learn from other cities and build capacity across departments.
- 4. Targeted communication** - Reach the most vulnerable with clear, accessible heat-risk info.

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Sweden's pathway Malmö

Keeping the City Cool

Malmö is a modern multicultural city that has converted heat from an industrial hub into a center of design, technology, and sustainability. It's innovatively recognized for integrating innovation, tradition, and green living. Its landscape blends medieval heritage with contemporary architecture, symbolizing Sweden's Turning Point. The city's specific pathway focuses on Rosengård, a low-income urban housing neighborhood, revealing both vulnerabilities and strong adaptive capacities.

LOCAL IMPACTS

- Rising temperatures
- Rising sea level

VULNERABILITIES

- Historic prioritization of winter-proof infrastructure
- Unprepared vulnerable groups of citizens, such as elderly or outdoor workers

RISKS AND CHALLENGES

- Heatwaves
- Unequal impacts of urban heat

The case study brought together a diverse group of **112 STAKEHOLDERS** from civil society and academia to the private sector and non-profit organizations. **Among those, two were the key partners.**

Municipality

Public Housing Company MKB

PARTICIPATORY PATHWAY

RECEPTION WORKSHOP (September 2022) → FOCUS GROUPS & INTERVIEWS (Summer 2024) → CO-CREATION WORKSHOP (January 2025)

RESULTS

CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT (Icon: Group of people) and EDUCATION (Icon: Book)

Spain - Urban and Rural Adaptation

From villages to cities, every voice matters in climate adaptation. In Aragón, climate challenges and solutions from both dimensions bridge countryside and urban settlements, reflecting the full diversity of our society.

Context

The region of Aragón is an autonomous community in northeastern Spain, characterized by a remarkable **variety of landscapes**, from the Pyrenean mountains and alpine valleys with glaciers, to rolling hills, deep canyons, the Ebro River basin, and vast steppes areas. It is also renowned for its **rich historical and ar-**

chitectural heritage, especially the **Mudéjar style**, which blends Islamic and Christian elements.

The regional capital is Zaragoza, the most populous city in Aragón, is a key hub for transportation, commerce, and logistics. The city

combines history and modernity: its compact, heritage-rich centre is home to numerous landmarks, while the surrounding districts have seen significant growth, especially in logistics and residential development. Zaragoza continues to expand with strong public services and a focus on **sustainable urban planning**, including **green infrastructure** and **eco-friendly neighbourhoods**.

Zaragoza has a **semi-arid climate** with Mediterranean influences. Summers are hot and dry, often exceeding 35°C, while winters are relatively mild. In recent years, however, the city has faced **significant climate challenges**, which have driven it to take proactive measures. Zaragoza is now recognized as a **leading city in climate adaptation**, with for example a Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan and implementing green infrastructure and urban revitalization.

Stakeholders

Government of Aragón

The Government of Aragón is striving to **keep pace with scientific knowledge**, which often moves faster than the implementation of policies and solutions across such a large and diverse region. While European funding provides crucial support, the government sometimes faces challenges related to limited human resources. A key point of convergence with the Adaptation AGORA project is the shared emphasis on **citizen participation**, which allows decision-makers to explore scenarios that would otherwise be difficult to identify. Another essential pillar for the government is **combating misinformation**.

Aragón is implementing several policy strategies, including the **Aragón Climate Change Strategy**, a living document that evolves alongside the region's economic and social development. The government is also advancing **nature-based solutions** and **spatial revitalization initiatives**. A flagship initiative is the **Aragón Climate Week**, a series of events in collaboration with institutions, associations, and private partners. This week-long program spans the region, providing **information, tools, and practical actions to support adaptation and mitigation efforts** for the entire Aragonese society.

Zaragoza City Council

The primary goal of Zaragoza is clear and ambitious: to become a **resilient and climate-neutral city by 2030**. The city is addressing climate change through a broad range of actions, fully aligned with European Union and national policies. Zaragoza is implementing measures within its **adaptation plan**, as well

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as initiatives linked to the mission of "**smart and climate-neutral cities**," of which it is an active member.

The connection with the Adaptation AGORA project lies primarily in **citizen participation**: listening to residents' voices, understanding their needs, and involving them in decision-making. Equally important is ensuring that these decisions are **communicated effectively**, minimizing the risk of **misinformation or misunderstanding**.

University of Zaragoza

The academic world in Zaragoza represented a stakeholder genuinely open to dialogue, sharing a mindset aligned with the project's approach. The University of Zaragoza strives to remain **engaged with society** rather than isolating itself within a bubble of publications and research. It aims to serve as an example

of **good governance, fostering proactive attitudes and a mindset open to change**. Research must go **hand in hand with citizens** and their needs, to truly **understand the gaps and challenges society faces** at any given moment. Only by doing so can research become genuinely useful, helping to **address societal problems and tackle global challenges** effectively.

Civil Society

From the perspective of social innovators, the key priority is to **place people at the centre of decision-making processes**. Achieving this goes beyond simply following a participatory approach; it requires ensuring that **all citizen profiles** are considered. **Inclusion is a fundamental pillar** of any process aimed at developing solutions that truly serve the city, society, and the residents who live within it. Citizens must become **active agents of change**, enabling them to see their ideas and solutions materialize in ways that are well-suited to their social and geographical environments.

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Challenges

The Aragón region, located in northeastern Spain, is particularly vulnerable to **water scarcity, biodiversity loss, and environmental degradation** due to its semi-arid conditions and geographic diversity stretching from the Pyrenees to the Ebro Valley. In recent years, the region has faced **rising temperatures, prolonged droughts, and increasingly frequent wildfires**. Projections point to more intense heatwaves and a **growing risk of desertification**, especially in lowland agricultural areas where crop yields and livestock production, such as pig farming, already suffer from heat stress and high irrigation demands.

Aragón's main vulnerabilities stem from its heavy reliance on water-intensive agriculture, combined with demographic challenges such as **rural depopulation and ageing communities in isolated areas**. These dynamics reduce the adaptive capacity of local economies and **exacerbate social inequalities**. Low-income and elderly populations, in both rural and urban contexts, are especially exposed, often lacking access to sufficient cooling systems, resilient infrastructure, or the financial means to implement adaptation measures. Despite a robust climate strategy aligned with

national and EU frameworks, Aragón continues to face significant hurdles in translating plans into local action. More effective coordination, funding, and regulatory support are urgently needed.

Urban centres like Zaragoza, where most of the pilot activities took place, face intensified **urban heat island effects** and heightened **flood risks from extreme rainfall**. With annual precipitation both scarce and unevenly distributed, the city is **increasingly vulnerable to droughts and heatwaves**. The heat island effect is particularly acute in older, densely built areas, while social inequalities, such as the lack of green spaces in lower-income neighbourhoods, further exacerbate these challenges.

Energy poverty remains also a pressing challenge in cities like Zaragoza, affecting vulnerable communities and limiting access to essential energy services. This topic was addressed in a **webinar exploring ways**, together with the Municipality of Almada (Portugal) and Valencia (Spain), two followers of the Adaptation AGORA project and the city of Barcelona.

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Participatory pathway

1. General structure

The project's four pilot areas served as testing grounds for inclusive, community-led climate adaptation. Starting in 2023, each area followed a **structured participatory pathway**: an inception workshop to map key stakeholders, engage different target audiences and decision-makers, and identify local barriers and vulnerabilities; followed by focus groups with specific populations to better understand their concerns and unique perspectives; and culminating in a final co-creation workshop aimed at developing actionable proposals and contributions to adaptation measures. **The emphasis was on soft adaptation measures**, non-structural, low-cost actions like public education and early warning systems, that address real community needs without heavy infrastructure.

Across the broader Aragón region, **93 stakeholders** from public institutions, civil society, health infrastructure, and business sectors were identified and actively engaged during the inception workshop. This approach effectively bridged community insights with policymaking, laying the groundwork for robust networks and long-term impact.

2. Inception workshop

September 2023: One of the core pillars of the Adaptation AGORA project is **inclusion**. To better understand both the adaptive capacity and the adaptation gap in Aragón, **two inception workshops** were organised: one in **Valderrobres**, the main town in the **rural area of Matarranya** and another in **Zaragoza**, where most pilot activities were concentrated. These workshops provided an initial partici-

patory diagnosis of the region's exposure to climate change, **bridging perspectives from both rural and urban contexts**.

In Zaragoza, participants identified **desertification, water scarcity, extreme temperatures, and the wider impacts of climate change on health and social inequalities** as the most pressing risks. Through participatory methods such as impact mapping and topic prioritisation, key entry points for co-creation emerged, particularly around **social inequality and water-related vulnerabilities**.

Discussions highlighted **urban-rural disparities**, ageing populations, and the concentration of vulnerable communities as central challenges. In Zaragoza, participants also emphasised the need to tackle broader socio-spatial injustices alongside climate risks.

The workshops concluded with a shared recognition that critical issues such as **social inequality, public health, and water poverty** must serve as priority areas for action. These themes were later further explored through citizen and stakeholder co-creation within the Adaptation AGORA focus groups.

3. Focus groups

In Zaragoza, as in the other pilot regions, the **Summer 2024** focus groups engaged specific target groups: **young people, workers, multicultural communities, and a group of elderly residents from the rural area of Matarranya**. In the rural area, rather than following a rigid co-creation methodology, the session created open conversational spaces where participants could share personal stories, such as memories of past heatwaves.

In Zaragoza, the focus group's proposals centred on the **social dimensions of adaptation**, particularly inequality and the limited responsiveness of institutions. Participants underlined the **importance of education** not only as a tool to raise awareness but also as a way to strengthen critical thinking. They highlighted that education could play a decisive role in countering misinformation, fostering **informed engagement**, and promoting both social inclusion and active participation in climate action.

to refine, prioritise, and further co-create solutions around these **citizen-identified needs**. There, participants engaged in exercises to refine collaboratively and prioritise soft adaptation solutions initially identified during the earlier focus groups.

4. Co-creation workshop

At the **beginning of 2025**, in Zaragoza, the final co-creation workshop was built directly on the local concerns, vulnerabilities, and proposals co-developed by citizens, using the focus groups outcomes as a basis. During the focus groups, themes such as **urban heat, social inequality, rural-urban disconnection, and working conditions** were highlighted. The need for public infrastructure that supports resilience (e.g., **climate shelters**), for improving the working conditions during heatwaves, and for inclusive public awareness strategies, were part of the discussions. These insights were not only taken forward as topics during the final co-creation workshop but also helped shape its structure, which was devised

Results

Adaptation to climate change is not only about technical solutions but about inclusion, fairness, and listening to communities

The co-creation sessions in Zaragoza brought forward a set of soft adaptation solutions that link **climate resilience with social inclusion**. Participants emphasised that adaptation must not only respond to environmental risks but also address inequalities, depopulation, and gaps in governance. Across the groups, there was a clear preference for community-led, low-cost initiatives that **foster partici-**

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ation, trust, and fairness, rather than purely technological approaches.

Youth highlighted the vulnerability of precarious and outdoor workers to extreme heat and prioritised improvements in working conditions. They also advocated for the creation of **climate shelters as safe and accessible cooling spaces** during heatwaves, and for **policies that strengthen urban-rural connections**, including ones to support young people in reconnecting with smaller villages, where climate pressures might be lower and more sustainable lifestyles could be encouraged. Young people called for **climate education** in schools and more inclusive communication strategies to counter misinformation with constructive, action-oriented narratives.

Workers echoed concerns about **heat stress** and like youth, they identified **climate shelters and cooling infrastructure** (shaded areas, hydration points) as urgent priorities. **Multicultural communities** proposed solu-

tions that integrate **environmental measures with social equity**. This included **recreation, the creation of energy communities to make renewable energy more inclusive, and clearer renewable energy policies** accessible to marginalised groups. Importantly, they emphasised **inclusive and multilingual communication** to reach linguistically diverse communities and advocated for gender-sensitive climate migration policies.

Elderly participants in rural Matarranya contributed practical knowledge from past experiences, including coping strategies for heatwaves, while raising concerns about **riverbed maintenance to reduce flooding risks** and about the impacts of prolonged droughts.

These insights highlight how citizens in Zaragoza view adaptation as inseparable from **inclusion, fairness, and everyday community life, making social justice the foundation of resilience**.

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Spain's pathway

Aragón region

Urban and Rural Adaptation

The region of Aragón is an astrosensory community in northwestern Spain, characterised by a remarkable variety of landscapes and renowned for its rich historical and cultural heritage. The region capital is Zaragoza, the most populous city in Aragón. It is key hub for transportation, commerce, and agriculture. Zaragoza has a semi-arid climate with Mediterranean influences, in recent years, however, the city has faced significant climate challenges, which have driven it to take proactive measures.

LOCAL IMPACTS	VULNERABILITIES	RISKS AND CHALLENGES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rising temperatures Extreme rainfalls Prolongued droughts Increase in wildfires frequencies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Semi-arid climate rises vulnerability for water scarcity, biodiversity loss, and environmental degradation, and desertification Rural depopulation and ageing communities in isolated area Energy poverty limiting access to essential energy services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Floods Heatwaves Urban heat island effect Exacerbation of social inequalities

STAKEHOLDERS who have been involved belonged to **4 key groups**.

Government of Aragón

Zaragoza City Council

University of Zaragoza

Civil Society

PARTICIPATORY PATHWAY

INCEPTION WORKSHOP

September 2023

FOCUS GROUPS

Summer 2024

CO-CREATION WORKSHOP

February 2025

CLIMATE SHELTERS

ENERGY COMMUNITIES

INCLUSIVE AND MULTILINGUAL COMMUNICATION

Germany - Go where citizens are

Citizen engagement is a challenging journey. But it becomes truly meaningful when we step into people's spaces, listen to their voices, and meet them where they are, rather than expecting them to come to us.

Context

Dresden, the capital of Saxony in eastern Germany, is set along the banks of the Elbe River and its valley, once recognized as a UNESCO World Heritage Site. Known as the "Florence on the Elbe", the city is celebrated for its **baroque architecture, rich cultural legacy, and**

abundant green spaces. Dresden's history is marked by **resilience as much as by beauty.** Since 1989, like many major urban centers in Saxony, the city has experienced steady population decline due to migration to the former West Germany. Yet demographic shifts

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tell only part of its story. Over the centuries, Dresden endured **repeated devastation**: a great fire in 1499, Prussian bombings in 1760, the violent suppression of the 1849 constitutional protests, and most tragically, the Allied air raids of 1945, which left much of the **city in ruins.**

The urban fabric today reflects both continuity and renewal. The **Altstadt (Old Town)**, with its Renaissance and baroque landmarks, has seen many of its **iconic buildings meticulously reconstructed** to their former grandeur after wartime destruction. Across the river, the **Neustadt (New Town)** serves as both a **residential and governmental hub**, renowned for its vibrant cultural scene, contemporary art, and lively nightlife, an alternative and creative counterbalance to the historic center.

Dresden is also one of **Germany's greenest cities**: over **40% of its territory** is covered by forests, parks, and open spaces. This commitment to preserving the natural environment is reflected in the **city's planning and development strategies.** At the same time, Dresden's context, shaped by **ageing infrastructure, demographic challenges, and urban growth**, has fostered a pragmatic, institutionally focused approach to **climate adaptation and sustainable development.**

but also created entry points to reach specific target groups and citizens. In many cases, stakeholders acted as bridges, enabling more direct and active engagement with the public.

Through this collaboration, the project gained valuable know-how and a deeper understanding of the challenges involved in reaching target populations. One key lesson was that it is often more effective to go where citizens are, in their own spaces and contexts, rather than simply inviting them to come to the project.

Stakeholders

The stakeholders involved in this pilot case study were diverse, ranging from institutions in the **health sector to private companies, associations, and representatives of the municipal administration.** The process of mapping stakeholders in each pilot region not only provided an overview of relevant actors

The city of Dresden

Another key stakeholder in the Dresden pilot case was the **municipality** itself. In recent years, the city has been experiencing a range of **climate change impacts, including heatwaves, rising temperatures, and flooding.** One of the main priorities for the administration has been addressing extreme heat, which

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grows more intense with each passing year. Since 2017, an interdisciplinary team of researchers and operational partners has been working on how urban neighborhoods and buildings can **better adapt to summer heat.** From this effort, the **HeatResilientCity project** was launched: a transdisciplinary initiative aimed at exploring how **densely populated districts**, such as Dresden-Gorbitz, and their residents can be **protected from extreme heat.**

Following the **record-breaking temperatures of July 2023**, the project also produced a **"HeatResilientCity"** for professionals in the health, social, educational, and housing sectors. The handbook provides practical **guidance on preventing and managing the impacts of heatwaves**, with a strong focus on the Gorbitz district. It includes information on Dresden's urban climate, introduces the **health consequences of extreme heat**, and highlights the specific factors that contribute to **heat stress** in the neighborhood.

Building on these efforts, the city is also developing a comprehensive **Heat Protection Plan** to **safeguard public health against increasingly frequent and intense heatwaves.** Across all these actions, Dresden's administration places strong emphasis on citizen engagement, recognizing that effective adaptation requires the **active involvement of residents.** The collaboration with the project has been instrumental in strengthening the city's **know-how on how to meaningfully involve its citizens in co-developing climate adaptation solutions.**

The Municipal Hospital

The participation of **Dresden's municipal hospital** as one of the city's key stakeholders proved particularly important, as it shed light on the complex relationship between **health**

care and climate change. This relationship is bidirectional, and it was explored in depth thanks to the involvement of healthcare professionals in the project's activities. For example, nurses experience the direct impact of **extreme heat and heatwaves** in their daily work, yet they can also play an active role in advancing **adaptation measures within the hospital.** These measures not only enable them to **work under better conditions** but also ensure that patients, who often feel the effects of climate change most acutely, either by developing new conditions or by upgrading pre-existing ones, **receive appropriate care** in a safe and livable environment.

More broadly, the health sector in Germany is responsible for around **6% of national greenhouse gas emissions.** For this reason, the municipal hospital is actively pursuing emission reduction strategies while also working to develop **adaptation solutions**, efforts that have been further strengthened through its participation in and collaboration with Adaptation AGORA.

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Private Sector - Sandstorm

The city of Dresden is already implementing a variety of **digital tools** and online platforms to meet the needs of residents who are comfortable engaging through these channels, as well as to address a wide range of needs related to city resources that are not widely known. A clear example is the **city's thematic map**, available on the municipal website, which highlights the locations of **free drinking water in Dresden.**

The city's commitment to exploring digital tools as solutions to specific needs is already evident. One of the stakeholders attending the co-creation workshop was **Sandstorm**, a digital agency that combines technology, design, and sustainability to deliver bespoke digital solutions. With a strong focus on sustainable practices, Sandstorm applies sustainable coding, developing efficient, low-resource software.

Sandstorm is the agency behind **Cleema**, a free mobile app for Android and iOS designed to **promote sustainable behaviour** in everyday life, with a particular focus on Dresden. Its main goal is to **engage and inform citizens on environmental issues**, encouraging participation in local initiatives and raising climate awareness. The app uses gamification elements, such as challenges and quizzes, to inspire daily action.

This philosophy mirrors the Adaptation AGORA project's approach in developing the **AGORA Quiz app**, also available for **Android** and **iOS.** Through an engaging, game-based format, the app invites citizens to explore the **science of climate change**, understand how it is communicated and sometimes distorted through disinformation, and learn about the core principles and practical measures of both adaptation and mitigation.

Non-profit Associations

The engagement with local non-profit associations proved equally valuable. A particularly active collaboration was established with **the International Garden Division**, a volunteer-driven **non-profit association** dedicated to community gardening, integration, education, and intercultural exchange. Much like Adaptation AGORA, the association **strives to give a voice to groups within society that are often unheard.**

Its main goal is to create a community garden in Dresden where people from different countries can grow fruit and vegetables on equal terms, while getting to know each other and exchanging ideas. The International Gardens Dresden provides a space for **personal initiative, self-organization, and the sharing of knowledge.**

At the heart of the initiative lies the strengthening of everyday democratic culture and, consequently, civil society. Values such as in-

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clusion, community participation, and network-building are closely aligned with the objectives of the project. The collaboration with the association offered practical and meaningful insights into citizen engagement.

Challenges

Dresden has an **oceanic climate with continental influences**, characterized by warm summers and relatively cold winters. In recent years, however, the city has become increasingly exposed to **rising temperatures**, drier summers, wetter winters, and **more frequent extreme weather events**. Vulnerability is further shaped by **rapid urbanisation, population growth, and socio-demographic dynamics** such as an ageing population. Densely built-up areas are particularly affected by the **urban heat island effect**, which amplifies **overheating, raises public health risks, and increases energy demand**. The city's location along the Elbe River and its tributaries also makes it highly susceptible

to **flooding** during episodes of heavy rainfall, as demonstrated by the **devastating floods of 2002 and 2013**. More recently, flash floods and overloaded drainage systems have become increasingly common due to **intense precipitation and rising groundwater levels**, pushing both the Elbe and urban water infrastructure to their limits. Urban expansion and extensive soil sealing have further reduced natural water retention, underlining the **urgent need for green infrastructure and decentralised rainwater management**.

At the same time, Dresden is facing **more frequent and intense storms and prolonged heatwaves**, all linked to ongoing climate change. These trends present significant **adaptation challenges across infrastructure, governance, and the economy**. Energy systems, transport networks, and tourism infrastructure remain highly vulnerable to climate-induced disruptions.

In response, the city has launched several adaptation initiatives, including the **"Schwammstadt Project"** (Sponge City Project), which adopts the **sponge city approach to enhance resilience**. The concept **reimagines the**

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urban landscape as a resilient ecosystem designed to naturally absorb, store, filter, and reuse rainwater, reducing surface runoff and flood risks while recharging groundwater and improving the local microclimate. Despite these efforts, progress remains uneven. Fragmented governance structures, outdated building codes, and limited financial resources continue to slow the pace of adaptation.

insights with policymaking, laying the groundwork for robust networks and long-term impact.

The activities successfully involved key societal groups, including **youth actively engaged in climate action, working populations in the health sector, multicultural communities, people with disabilities and seniors**. Particular attention was given to ensuring broad representation across public authorities, local communities, civil society organizations, academia and research institutions, the private sector, and the media.

Participatory pathway

1. General structure

The project's four pilot areas served as testing grounds for inclusive, community-led climate adaptation. Starting in 2023, each area followed a structured participatory pathway: an inception workshop to map key stakeholders, engage different target audiences and decision-makers, and identify local barriers and vulnerabilities; followed by focus groups with specific populations to better understand their concerns and unique perspectives; and culminating in a final co-creation workshop aimed at developing actionable proposals and contributions to adaptation measures. **The emphasis was on soft adaptation measures**, non-structural, low-cost actions like public education and early warning systems, that address real community needs without heavy infrastructure.

In Dresden, **256 stakeholders** from public institutions, civil society, health infrastructure, and business sectors were identified and actively engaged during the inception workshop. This approach effectively bridged community

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2. Inception workshop

September 2023: The inception workshop in Dresden explored key climate-related risks, with **heatwaves and heavy rainfalls and floods** considered as the primary hazards of concern. Participants discussed how these risks affect the urban environment, including impacts on infrastructure, housing, and individual well-being. While both hazards were acknowledged, heatwaves emerged as a particularly pressing issue due to their increasingly frequent and prolonged occurrence in recent years. A central focus of the workshop was on how **social vulnerability intersects with climate risks**. Participants reflected on the fact that adaptation needs and capacities vary significantly across population groups. For example, senior residents and people with chronic illnesses or disabilities were seen as particularly at risk, especially when living in **poorly adapted housing** or alone, with limited access to information or support. Discussions also addressed **economic vulnerability**, such as limited access to air conditioning or other coping resources. From an inclusion and capacity perspective, the workshop highlighted several **barriers to adaptation**. These included limited public awareness, lack of institutional coordination, and **insufficient representation of vulnerable communities** in climate planning processes. At the same time, existing civil society initiatives, community-based networks, and the city's infrastructure for public engagement were mentioned as potential assets for supporting local adaptation responses.

ven to **accessibility and inclusivity**, including selecting convenient locations, archiving sessions outside typical working hours, and adopting facilitation strategies to the needs of specific target groups. Each session began with a brief preparatory phase designed to establish a shared understanding of the session's objectives and to create a welcoming, comfortable environment for participants.

Summer 2024: In Dresden the first focus group involved **youth actively engaged in climate action**. Two additional focus groups engaged **professional caregivers** working in a public hospital. Another group consisted of participants from **multicultural communities**, who proposed several soft adaptation measures inspired by **traditional knowledge** from their countries of origin and adapted to the local context.

3. Focus groups

The co-creation of **soft climate adaptation solutions** was carried out through a series of focus groups across the four pilot regions. Across all pilots, particular attention was gi-

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In Dresden, the co-creation process also extended to **vulnerable populations**, in addition to the target groups common across the other pilot regions. This was addressed through two separate focus groups: one with **seniors**, and another with **people with disabilities and chronic illnesses**. The latter group developed a set of measures **prioritizing inclusive and accessible approaches to climate resilience**, ensuring that adaptation strategies responded to the specific needs of all community members.

Vulnerabilities and [the climate-health.com](https://www.climate-health.com/en/the-focus-of-a-dedicated-workshop-of-the-use-to-own-learning-series) [www.the-focus-of-a-dedicated-workshop-of-the-use-to-own-learning-series](https://www.climate-health.com/en/the-focus-of-a-dedicated-workshop-of-the-use-to-own-learning-series). The city of Dresden shared experiences and views with Grenoble and Barcelona.

4. Co-creation workshop

At the beginning of 2025 the final co-creation workshops were organised with the common purpose all over the four pilot regions to work on **citizen-generated ideas** from previous phases, evaluate their **feasibility and relevance**, and identify meaningful strategies for their implementation through **inclusive engagement methods**. In Dresden, thematic sub-workshops were organised around four adaptation topics:

1. **Effective Climate Communication**
2. **Participatory City Design** (including Digital tools)
3. **Educational initiatives in schools**
4. **Financing climate adaptation**

These formed the basis for collaborative refinement, allowing participants to explore how the ideas emerging from the previous focus groups could be translated into concrete, actionable measures at the local level.

Results

Voicing the voiceless: awareness, citizen engagement and building a network

During the last co-creation workshop participants consolidated proposals from all focus groups into a few key directions: shifting from fear-based to inclusive messaging, enhancing digital participatory tools with features like mapping shaded areas and water points, promoting school-based awareness campaigns with hands-on learning and intergenerational exchange, and identifying funding strategies that integrate adaptation into existing city budgets.

Different groups brought different needs and perspectives during focus groups meetings:

- **Youth** in Dresden proposed a **school-based awareness campaign on climate adaptation**.

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combining hands-on climate education with community-led action groups. They emphasized that engagement should be enjoyable, accessible, and voluntary to be effective.

Professional caregivers highlighted the dual challenge of safeguarding their own wellbeing while ensuring patient care. Proposed measures included **heat-triggered protocols, more flexible work schedules, and adaptable work clothing systems**, addressing both health protection and care standards.

Multicultural communities focused on raising awareness and building solidarity around visible, everyday adaptation practices. They suggested soft adaptation measures inspired by **traditional knowledge** from their countries of origin, such as **passive cooling techniques** like using stored rainwater to water rooftops during heat events.

Vulnerable populations, seniors and people with disabilities and chronic illnesses, developed measures reflecting their specific needs, particularly regarding extreme heat. They showed interest in accessible engagement formats, including surveys and online platforms, and expressed willingness to act as public representatives for campaigns **promoting inclusive climate adaptation**. Participants stressed the importance of inclusive formats, such as audio descriptions and simplified language, to ensure information reaches all community members.

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Tuscan-Etruscan Apennines in northern Italy, from Copernicus Sentinel-2/ESA

Voices

Meet the people behind the process, from the project team members to local stakeholders, policymakers, institutions, NGOs, academics, and everyday citizens. Each voice offers a unique perspective, sharing their experiences, ideas, and contributions to shaping place-based adaptation journeys. Together, they bring to life the rich, collective effort driving local resilience across Europe.

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Germany's pathway Dresden

Go where Citizens are

Dresden, the capital of Saxony along the Elbe River, is known for its baroque architecture, cultural heritage, and extensive green spaces. Its beauty and resilience, marked by fires, bombings, and major reconstruction after 1945. Today, the Altstadt (Old Town) reflects restored historic grandeur, while the Neustadt (New Town) offers a vibrant cultural and residential scene. In this context, the city has embraced a pragmatic, institution-driven approach to sustainability and climate adaptation.

LOCAL IMPACTS

- Rising temperatures
- Intense precipitation
- Rising groundwater level

VULNERABILITIES

- 60% of territory covered in green spaces and the city is committed to preserve it
- Location along the Elbe river
- Population growth & rapid urbanization
- Aging population & infrastructure

RISKS AND CHALLENGES

- Floods
- Overloaded drainage systems
- Urban heat island effect
- Increased energy demand

STAKEHOLDERS

were mapped across each city region, reaching citizens in their own spaces and contexts. Those involved belonged to 4 key groups.

- Municipality
- Municipal Hospital
- Private sector
- Non-profit associations

PARTICIPATORY PATHWAY

RESULTS

The "Voices" Gallery

Scan the QR code to dive into the gallery.

Hear firsthand stories from the people who contributed to shaping the project and **browse by media type or location** to explore different perspectives.

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ERS-2 radar view of Strait of Messina, Italy (E534)

Glossary

Discover the language of climate adaptation. This glossary offers clear, accessible definitions of key terms to help you navigate the complex world of climate adaptation, from policies and practices to people and processes. Whether you're a newcomer or a seasoned expert, these terms will support deeper understanding and more informed action.

The language of Climate Adaptation

Below are some of the key words shaping the **Voices of Climate Adaptation glossary**. Click [here](#) to explore and learn more.

Adaptation

Adjustment in natural or human systems in response to actual or expected climatic stimuli or their effects, which moderates harm or exploits beneficial opportunities. Various types of adaptation can be distinguished, including anticipatory and reactive adaptation, private and public adaptation, and autonomous and planned adaptation

Capacity Building

The process by which individuals or organizations obtain, improve, or refine the skills, knowledge, tools, equipment, or other resources to do their work competently

Climate change disinformation

Climate disinformation is the intentional dissemination of false information related to climate change and climate action. It can take many forms, from hard denial and conspiracy theories to softer, more insidious disinformation that seeks to muddy the waters by claiming that climate change is not man-made or as bad as scientists are saying and therefore requires no urgent action.

Citizen Engagement

Refers to the active participation of individuals and communities in governance processes, encompassing decision-making, implementation, and monitoring

Co-creation

Collaboratively creating outputs like tools or policy recommendations. A process that can add value and increase innovative potential through intertribal experience design

Public Awareness

A process that seeks to inform and educate people about a topic or issue with the intention of influencing their attitudes, behaviours and beliefs towards the achievement of a defined purpose or goal.

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www.voicesofclimateadaptation.datscims.com

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